

Ocean Acidification

Exploring effects of changing atmospheric CO₂ upon marine ecosystems

Ocean Acidification – a teaching guide

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Preface

This work is one of a series intended to assist in the teaching of ocean literacy and allied aspects of environmental education. It targets investigations on the effects of ocean acidification on the functioning of the plankton that support the growth of most organisms in open-water aquatic ecosystems.

The work requires the use of simulation models. These models enable students to experiment with simple representations of the real world, to explore for themselves what the consequences are of changing ocean acidity.

The models operate within a **Microsoft Windows** application, called **Powersim Cockpit**, which is available for free.

To download this free application, visit this website:

<https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>

WARNING: Only install Cockpit on a PC that does not contain another Powersim Studio product. Installing Powersim Cockpit if you already have a version of Powersim Studio installed will overwrite that version! The simulations will operate within other Studio applications.

Acknowledgement to Funders

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Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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The simulation models associated with this work was developed using the software **Powersim Studio 10** (www.Powersim.com), in part by ARK dynamics Ltd (www.ARKdynamics.org). The models presented here are free for use under the Powersim Cockpit platform.

GLOSSARY

Items in italics are described elsewhere in this glossary.

Acid: characterisation of an aqueous solution such that $[H^+] > [OH^-]$ and hence $pH < 7$.

Acidification: a process through which the $[H^+]$ is increased (and hence $[OH^-]$ decreases). pH thus decreases with acidification.

Acidity: a measure of the degree of being acidic. Given as $[H^+]$.

Alkali: characterisation of an aqueous solution such that $[H^+] < [OH^-]$ and hence $pH > 7$.

Alkalinity: a measure of the degree of being basic. Given as $[OH^-]$.

Alkalinisation: a process through which the $[H^+]$ is decreased (and hence $[OH^-]$ increases). pH thus increases with alkalinisation.

Base: characterisation of an aqueous solution such that $[H^+] < [OH^-]$ and hence $pH > 7$.

Basification: a process through which the $[H^+]$ is decreased (and hence $[OH^-]$ increases). pH thus increases with basification.

Buffer: specifically a pH buffer, is a combination of chemicals that restrict the change in pH when acid or alkali are added to the solution. In seawater, most of the buffering is provided by the *carbonate system*. Buffers have an optimum pH, either side of which their buffering capacity declines.

Calcification: the deposition of $CaCO_3$ by organisms, typically as a skeletal structure. The process decreases the total *DIC* concentration, but actually increases *acidity* (pH decreases) through the consumption of CO_3^{2-} and thence a decrease in *alkalinity* (*TA*).

$CO_2(aq)$: free CO_2 in water. This is the actual substrate for the enzyme RuBisCO, as the first point of CO_2 -fixation in photosynthesis. Microalgae either take up $CO_2(aq)$ from the water, or they use HCO_3^- and use the enzyme carbonic anhydrase to liberate $CO_2(aq)$.

Consumption: biologically, the breakdown of biomass leading to the generation of energy and conversion of part of the consumed biomass into the biomass of the consumer. Typically this involves the partial conversion of carbon (C) as C-biomass into CO_2 through respiration. The consequence of the respiration is thus the addition of CO_2 to the environment. Consumption is thus the opposite of *production*.

Carbonate system: a combination of different components of dissolved inorganic carbon (*DIC*), as $CO_2(aq)$, carbonic acid, carbonate and bicarbonate. The carbonate system plays a critical role in controlling the acidity (pH) of seawater by providing a *buffer* against pH change. See [Fig.5](#).

DIC: dissolved inorganic carbon; the sum of all forms of inorganic C dissolved in water.

δ : rate of change in a value, thus units include 'per time' ($time^{-1}$, for example as d^{-1}). The symbol is Greek lowercase 'delta'.

Δ : change in; a value, with no reference to the rate of that change; no reference to the amount of time taken to achieve that change. The symbol is Greek uppercase 'delta'.

$[H^+]$: concentration of hydrogen ions, i.e. of protons, H^+ . Units in oceanography are typically as moles Kg^{-1} of seawater. The $[]$ denotes concentration.

OA: ocean acidification.

[OH⁻]: concentration of hydroxyl ions, i.e. of OH⁻. Units in oceanography are typically as moles Kg⁻¹ of seawater. The [] denotes concentration.

pH: log reciprocal transform of the proton concentration. (see also [H⁺])

Production: biologically, the formation of biomass, which typically involves the conversion of carbon (C) in CO₂ into C-biomass through photosynthesis. The consequence of production is thus the removal of CO₂. Production is thus the opposite of *consumption* and respiration.

Proton: hydrogen (H) ion, i.e., H⁺

Revelle factor: A measure of the ability of the ocean to resist changes in acidity; a higher Revelle factor indicates lower buffering capacity.

Total alkalinity (TA): sum of all negatively charged ions which characterises the buffering capacity of the water. In seawater, the dominant component is bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻), and hence TA changes with *pH* as the contribution of HCO₃⁻ within the total dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) alters.

OVERARCHING SUMMARY

- Acidity is typically described using the pH scale. Water of high acidity has a low pH; water with low acidity (also termed high 'alkalinity' or highly 'basic') has a high pH. Neutrality is pH 7. The pH of the ocean is now ca. pH 8.1; the ocean is therefore weakly basic.
- The pH scale is logarithmic, so a pH change of 1 unit equates to a 10-fold change in acidity.
- Acidity (measured as pH) is an important factor affecting biological processes. The pH of water is especially important for the smallest organisms that grow in the ocean ('microplankton') because they have a relatively greater surface area in contact with the water. Marine organisms evolve to optimise growth at a certain seawater pH and may be more, or less, sensitive to changes in pH.
- About 30% of the CO₂ produced by humans using fossil fuels enters the ocean.
- When CO₂ dissolves in seawater, the acidity increases (that is, the sea water pH decreases). The acidity of the ocean has increased by ca. 25% since the industrial revolution (ca. 200 years ago; pH was approximately 8.2). This ongoing process is called **ocean acidification**.
- Changes in the acidity of seawater are controlled ('buffered') by interactions between different forms of inorganic carbon dissolved in water (between CO₂, bicarbonate and carbonate). That buffering is strongest around pH 8.2 and is becoming less effective as ocean acidification moves the baseline pH lower.
- Biological processes affect acidity. Photosynthesis uses CO₂ and decreases acidity (pH increases), while the use of biomass by consumers (animals, bacteria) produces CO₂ and increases acidity (pH decreases). This oscillation in pH can be seen between day and night (as photosynthesis only functions in day light), and across the seasons as populations grow and decay.
- Under ocean acidification, the biological cycles of pH occur at a lower baseline pH level and, because the pH buffering is poorer, the oscillations become larger. Collectively, these changes cause stresses on individual organisms and hence on the functioning of the whole ecosystem.
- Overall effects of ocean acidification on marine ecology will be mixed, and impacts on a given organism may be direct (pH affects their wellbeing) or indirect (prey or predators may be affected). Ocean acidification represents one of many factors affecting organisms; effects of multiple stressors (such as changes in temperature and nutrient load) may well combine to make matters worse again.
- Because the ocean is so large, and it takes many decades or even hundreds of years for water to travel through the deep ocean and back to the surface where most marine life occurs, the effects of ocean acidification will likely persist for a very long time. Eventually, though, thousands of years of continuing addition of sediments from rivers will naturally add chemicals that will neutralize ocean acidification.
- There are two main approaches to prevent or reverse ocean acidification; they are not mutually exclusive. One approach depends on adding chemicals to neutralise acidity (though at best this could only delay acidification because the amount of chemicals required is very large). The alternative approach is to prevent or minimise further CO₂ addition to the atmosphere (by decreasing or halting the use of fossil fuels) which would otherwise enter the ocean to increase acidity.

INTRODUCTION

Ocean acidification (OA) is a process through which the acidity of the ocean increases in consequence of the addition of carbon dioxide (CO₂). Events involved in OA, in the interpretation of the effects of changes in acidity, are complex, and require an understanding of many features of physics, chemistry and biology.

This teaching guide seeks to support teachers in explaining the topic of ocean acidification to students of different ages. It contains some suggestions to stimulate teacher-led in-class discussions. It also offers simulation models that can be downloaded and run on a computer. These require the installation of a free application (Powersim Studio Cockpit) that runs under the MS Windows operating system.

This guide is the third in a series on the subject of ocean and water literacy. The others, which should ideally be studied before this, are:

Flynn KJ (2024). Exploring eutrophication – polluting with too much of a good thing; a teaching guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12529789>

Flynn KJ, Lessin G (2025) Getting too warm: exploring effects of temperature upon aquatic ecosystems – a teaching guide. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/17522204>

Fit to curriculum

This document is best directed to students aged ca. 13 years and above. With care, however, the basic concepts can be taught to younger students, from ca. 8 years.

While this guide provides an introduction to the topic and suggestions for classroom activities, the teacher is best equipped to select what topics to draw to the attention of their class, how best to work through these topics, where to start and stop.

The **OVERARCHING SUMMARY** provides a core overview of the topic, but each subsection also contains its own summary.

Inevitably, when considering ocean acidification, a major part of the topic revolves around the subject of ‘acidity’. The material provided here goes into some detail on this, but the teacher will need to extract what they feel is most suitable and to explain matters using terminology consistent with the student age and curriculum.

Some seemingly obvious but also particularly confusing issues for many students are that:

- a **low** pH equates to a **higher** acidity.
- the opposite of ‘**acid**’ is ‘**base**’ or ‘**alkali**’.
- ‘**acidification**’ means to make water more acidic; importantly, it has nothing to do with whether the water was originally acidic (pH<7) or basic (pH>7).
- the opposite of ‘acidification’ is ‘**basification**’, which is to make water more basic; again, it has nothing to do with whether the water was originally acidic (pH<7) or basic (pH>7).

The topic of ocean acidification is of greatest importance to the plankton that support life in the sea. For an overview and introduction to plankton, see:

[The Plankton Manifesto - A call for Plankton-Based Solutions to address The Triple Planetary Crisis \(biodiversity, climate & pollution\) | UN Global Compact](#)

Starting the conversation – some simple experiments

Limewater and chalk

A good place to start for young students is the classic simple experiment of blowing into limewater to test for the presence of CO₂. This experiment demonstrates one facet of the carbonate system that is at the heart of pH-regulation in the oceans.

The reaction takes limewater (a saturated solution of calcium hydroxide) and combines it with CO₂ to make calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) and water. The calcium carbonate produced in the test is so concentrated that it precipitates (hence the ↓ in the equation), forming a cloudy suspension.

In marine organisms, this same CaCO₃ is used to make shells. Limestone cliffs, such as the White Cliffs of Dover in England, are the product of hundreds of millions of years of the activity of microscopic plankton, themselves covered with structures made of CaCO₃. We can see the growth of such organisms today from satellite images (Fig.1), making the water a milky colour that reflects light.

Fig.1 Under certain conditions, the microscopic marine coccolithophorid microalga *Emiliana huxleyi* (see Fig.4a,b) can form massive blooms detectable by satellite remote sensing. The white clouds in the water are from light reflected from billions of coccoliths (minute plates of chalky calcium carbonate, CaCO₃) floating in the water-column. Sinking to be deposited on the seabed, and then compressed over geological time, this material forms chalk (limestone) deposits. The image is of the southwest UK, taken by the Landsat satellite, July 1999; image courtesy of Steve Groom, NEODAAS, Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

Measuring seawater pH

If you have access to a pH probe, then it is relatively simple to undertake some simple titration experiments to determine pH of a solution of either real seawater or (ideally) artificial seawater.

WARNING: any samples of water taken from the natural environment should be treated with care (do not ingest, wash hands after contact, etc.) as they may contain pathogens.

Artificial seawater salts can be obtained from any shop selling marine aquaria supplies. It is useful to look at the 'ingredients' list on the packet, noting that while sodium and chloride (Na, Cl) and various others (K, Mg, Ca, S) are the most important constituents, quite high up in the list will also be 'carbonate' and/or 'bicarbonate'. These two components, carbonate and bicarbonate (CO_3^- and HCO_3^- , respectively), provide the acidity regulator for the seawater. A litre volume of this seawater is quite sufficient. Be sure to aerate the suspension overnight to achieve an equilibrium between the CO_2 in the water and that in the atmosphere.

A standard laboratory pH probe is not designed for use in seawater (with all that salt) so it may not calibrate properly. However, for the task at hand this is not important. The measured pH should be around 8.2 – 8.4; that is the baseline pH of natural seawater several decades ago – it has since decreased due to 'ocean acidification', so the pH you measure may be less than this. In reality (as influencing an individual organism growing in the sea), pH is not constant (this is explored later in this document).

Dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) will now be required. The actual concentrations are not important, though 0.1M or 0.01M will suffice.

The experiment is to add measured amounts of acid or alkali to the solution to achieve different pH values, recording the pH after each addition of a set volume of acid or alkali. This should be repeated to cover a pH range of approximately pH 6.5 – pH 9.5. What should be observed is that around pH 8, the pH changes rather little for a given addition of acid or base. Below pH 7.5 and above pH 8.5, the same additions should make pH change more.

You may notice that measuring the pH of seawater, and how it changes when drops of acid or alkali are added, can be a slow business. The reason is because the pH of the seawater is buffered by the carbonate system. This will be explained in detail further below – in brief it relates to the balance between carbonate, bicarbonate and CO_2 . The pH value is slow to settle because the carbonate equilibrium is slow to achieve.

If the same experiment is done with diluted seawater, the pH will be seen to be more sensitive to additions: pure water, of course, contains no buffer and the smallest addition of HCl or NaOH will cause rapid and extreme pH changes.

Interpreting these results is not as straightforward as it may appear. pH is expressed on a logarithmic scale, and 'acidity' actually refers to the concentration of protons (H^+ ions) – both concepts will require age-appropriate explanation.

However, at the very least the experiment should clarify that:

- 1) the pH of seawater is far more resistant to additions of acid or alkali than is pure water
- 2) the buffering of pH is strongest at around pH 8 and becomes weaker (i.e. pH shifts more for a given addition of acid or alkali) away from the pH range of 7.5 – 8.5.

The importance of this for the organisms is that they evolved to grow at certain pH levels. Moving away from the optimum, organisms become increasingly stressed and, at extreme pH values, they will die.

ACIDITY

Summary

- Acidity is usually referenced by the pH value. pH is an inverse logarithmic scale of proton concentration (i.e., $\log_{10} (1/[H^+])$), which is the underlying measure of acidity.
- The concentration of protons is written as $[H^+]$, where '[']' indicates concentration.
- Acidification refers to an **increase** in $[H^+]$, which is a **decrease** in pH. It makes no difference whether the starting point is acid ($pH < 7$) or alkali ($pH > 7$): an increase in acidity is still an acidification.
- The opposite of acidification is basification, where the concentration of hydroxide ions $[OH^-]$ increases, while the concentration of protons $[H^+]$ decreases.
- Without a reference point, a given change in pH value could refer to changes in $[H^+]$ different by many orders of magnitude.
- What matters to organisms is the concentration of protons in the water, as $[H^+]$. Because pH is a log scale, a minor change in pH can equate to a significant change in actual acidity.

H^+ ions and the pH scale

Water, H_2O , contains very small concentrations of the ions H^+ (protons) and OH^- (hydroxide ions). **The term acidity refers to the concentration of protons in the water.**

An excess of H^+ over OH^- describes an **acid**, while an excess of OH^- over H^+ describes an alkali, otherwise termed a **base**.

If the concentrations of H^+ and OH^- are equal, then the water is neutral with respect to whether it is acidic or basic. If H^+ are added, or OH^- removed, then the process is an **acidification**. The opposite (removal of H^+ or addition of OH^-) is a **basification**.

The concentration of protons is written as $[H^+]$, with units of moles of protons per Kg of water.

Acidity is usually referred to in terms of pH. However, pH does not relate simply to $[H^+]$. The formal equation for pH is:

$$pH = \log_{10} \frac{1}{[H^+]}$$

or

$$pH = -1 \times \log_{10} [H^+]$$

You would use the following syntax in a spreadsheet formula:

$$pH = \log_{10}*(1/[H^+])$$

or

$$pH = -1*\log_{10}([H^+])$$

In words, *pH is the \log_{10} of the reciprocal of the proton concentration.*

The pH scale is normally considered over values of 1-14. A plot of $[H^+]$ against pH (**Fig.2**) shows two important consequences of the pH equation:

- i) The relationship is not linear: a change of 1 pH unit equates to a 10-fold change in proton concentration $[H^+]$.
- ii) The relationship is inverted: a high acidity equates to low pH.

Fig.2 Plots of acidity as proton concentration $[H^+]$ vs pH. Panel (a) shows the full pH range from 1-14 with $[H^+]$ on a linear scale, while (b) shows the same plot but now with $[H^+]$ on a log scale. Panels (c) and (d) show the same data but over the potential pH range seen in marine waters (6.5 – 9.5), and with $[H^+]$ now expressed as nanomoles (i.e., moles $\times 10^9$) rather than moles. Expressing $[H^+]$ as nanomoles gives a more convenient scale when considering ocean acidification, as values appear in the range of 1-100. Neutrality, at which point $[H^+] = [OH^-]$ is at $[H^+] = 10^{-7}$ moles ($=100$ nanomoles) proton Kg^{-1} , which is pH 7.

Why does this matter? Well, the interactions between acidity and the physiology of organisms relates to $[H^+]$ and not to pH. Chemists use the transform ‘pH’ to simplify their science and communication because chemists are concerned with ranges from very acidic (pH=1) to very alkali (pH=14). This range in pH equates to values of $[H^+]$ from $1E-1$ (i.e., 0.1) to $1E-14$ (i.e., 0.00000000000001) mole Kg^{-1} . It is much easier to talk about, and work with, numbers from 1 to 14, than with numbers between 0.1 and 0.00000000000001!

Neutrality is $\text{pH}=7$, the point at which the concentrations of $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ are equal, each at $1\text{E}-7$ mole Kg^{-1} .

The range of acidity that we are concerned with in the context of ocean acidification is around pH 7-10, with seawater having a pH of about 8. This range of acidity is thus $1\text{E}-7$ – $1\text{E}-10$ mole H^+ Kg^{-1} . This is a 1000-fold range in concentrations. Freshwater is often more acidic than seawater; we will come to the reason why in the section on the **CARBONATE SYSTEM & THE BUFFERING OF OCEAN pH** .

A warning about logarithmic ('log') scales

Other than pH , other frequently used \log_{10} transforms include decibels (dB) for sound, and the Richter scale, for earthquakes.

Log scales are used for these other topics for the same reason we use a log scale for $[\text{H}^+]$ in the form of pH ; the numbers are just easier to work with mathematically and also in communications (such as in graphs). Sometimes data are plotted on graphs using a log-axis (e.g. **Fig.2b,d** for $[\text{H}^+]$); sometimes (as with pH) the data are log-transformed and those transforms are plotted on a linear axis.

Always exercise great care when interpreting \log_{10} transformed data and also when viewing graphs with \log_{10} scales – often interpretations are not as straightforward as they may appear!

Ocean acidification terminology

There are two common topics related to the reporting of OA and acidity that need to be addressed before continuing.

- 1) Various reports make use of the term '*change in pH* ' (or '*delta pH* ', sometimes written as ΔpH), such as '*the change in pH was 0.5*'. Given that the physiology of organisms relates to $[\text{H}^+]$, while pH is a reciprocal \log_{10} transform, it should be apparent that a change in acidity by 0.5 pH units has a very different meaning if the starting pH was pH 9, pH 8 or pH 7. This can be seen from **Fig.2**. **For this reason, reference to 'changes in pH ' should be avoided, and if they must be used it is essential that a reference point of the initial (or final) pH value is also given.** In contrast, a 'change in acidity' (as in a $\Delta[\text{H}^+]$) is clear.
- 2) The ocean is alkaline, with a $\text{pH}>7$ (typically pH around 8). **Some commentators have, because the ocean water is basic (i.e., alkali), argued that *ocean acidification* is an inappropriate term; this argument is incorrect.** Acidification is the increase in the concentration of H^+ . The opposite process, the decrease in concentration of H^+ , is called *basification*. These terms refer to a change in concentration of H^+ and make no reference to the start or end point. As a comparison, consider that the warming of a room involves raising the temperature. It does not matter whether the initial temperature is -10°C or 10°C , the room still gets warmer if the temperature increases.

Class Activity

The acid-base relationship is vital for all life forms on Earth. Protons, H^+ , play a pivotal role in the physiology of all organisms. Protons are pumped across membranes, with the gradient of the proton concentrations either side of the membrane driving organism energetics. For example, proton gradients help to pump nutrients into a cell, or making ATP (adenosine triphosphate), the energy currency of living cells.

In addition, the reaction rates of enzymes that are involved in biochemical reactions each exhibit an optimal acidity range. If the acidity is higher or lower than the optimal, then the processes will not operate efficiently, and the organism will experience stress and eventually may die.

As an example of pH optimality for enzymes, consider that the digestive processes in the human stomach operate in a highly acidic environment; cells lining our stomach produce hydrochloric acid (HCl). If you suffer from 'heartburn', caused by excess acidity in your stomach, you may take calcium carbonate ($CaCO_3$) tablets to help to increase the stomach pH.

Discuss whether smaller or larger microorganisms, for example plankton of different sizes, may be more susceptible to changes in $[H^+]$, such as caused by ocean acidification.

For context, consider that the digestive enzymes operating in juvenile small zooplankton animals, such as a copepod, operate in a slightly basic environment, while those of larger adults being slightly acidic (Tang et al. 2011).

This topic is revisited in detail in [PHYSIOLOGICAL PROCESSES & OCEAN ACIDIFICATION](#), further below.

CHANGES TO ATMOSPHERIC CO₂ & EXCHANGE WITH THE OCEAN

Summary

- The concentration of CO₂ in the Earth atmosphere is very low, currently at approximately 0.043% of the total gas content.
- This level of CO₂ is a consequence of organisms transforming the previously very high atmospheric CO₂ levels into inorganic forms (calcium carbonate, through making shells and similar structures that form limestone) and into organic forms (via photosynthesis, resulting in what we now term fossil fuels). These processes have occurred over a vast period of time, starting approximately 2 billion years ago.
- The contribution of CO₂ to the atmosphere is described in terms of its partial pressure, as pCO₂.
- The units for pCO₂ differ between science subjects. In atmospheric science it is often reported as parts per million, or ppm.
- 1 ppm for a gas is 1 μL (10⁻⁶ L) in 1 L, which is 0.0001%. As of 2026, atmospheric pCO₂ levels are ca. 430ppm (=0.043%), having risen from a preindustrial level, 200 years ago, of <300ppm.
- CO₂ enters or leaves the ocean depending on the relative concentrations of gaseous CO₂ in the atmosphere and surface water (the latter being affected by carbonate chemistry, acidity and temperature) and also by factors affecting air flow at the air-water interface (waves, wind). Biological processes in the water also consume and produce CO₂.

CO₂ and Earth's geological history

Energy from the sun, mainly as shorter wavelengths energy, passes through the atmosphere, warming the planet surface and being converted to longer wavelength infrared energy. Earth temperature and the concentration of atmospheric CO₂ are linked because the latter is a gas that traps infrared energy and reflects it back to the planet. This is a crucial process for life, as without such so-called 'greenhouse gasses', Earth would be frozen. Another important greenhouse gas is water vapour; the warmer the planet, the more water vapour accumulates in the atmosphere. There are also other so-called greenhouse gasses in the atmosphere and other factors, such as cloud formation, that affect the temperature of the planet surface. Several of these are associated with plankton, including production of N₂O and even of clouds; some common plankton species release chemicals that in the upper atmosphere form the seed crystals for cloud formation. The wellbeing of ocean plankton communities has various important implications for Earth.

After Earth was formed, the atmosphere contained a very high concentration of CO₂. Some 2.5 billion years ago the contribution of CO₂ is thought to have been 25-50% of the air. Through the activity of (mainly photosynthetic) organisms, much of that CO₂ was converted into limestone and what we now extract as oil and gas. At the same time, the activity of the photosynthetic organisms that consumed CO₂ also released O₂. Eventually, the concentration of CO₂ was brought down to around 0.03% of the air, with O₂ at 21%. That concentration of CO₂ is low enough to start limiting photosynthesis by land plants, while the level of O₂ is high enough to more readily support combustion of those plants (as wildfires), and of course also supports the activity of organisms that consume plant material. This combination of CO₂ and O₂ concentrations could thus be seen as a balance point.

The concentration of a gas is a function of the temperature, pressure and the presence of other gasses. The amount of carbon dioxide, CO₂ in the current Earth atmosphere is historically (set against values

over the past 2 billion years) very low, at around 0.043%. This value is, nonetheless, higher than it has been for millions of years (Jurikova et al. 2025); humans and the ecology with which we interact developed during such a low CO₂ period.

Over its geological history, Earth, and life on Earth, has witnessed various and long-lived changes in the concentrations of atmospheric CO₂, in temperature. Because CO₂ dissolves in water to acidify it (see **CARBONATE SYSTEM & THE BUFFERING OF OCEAN pH**, below), there are also wide variations in ocean acidity. Indeed, life on Earth has witnessed extremes of temperature and in atmospheric CO₂ far beyond the values we currently measure.

Over time, life evolves to best equip organisms with an ability to maximise survival in the conditions experienced by those organisms. Concerns expressed now, with respect to the values of atmospheric CO₂ and temperature, are not associated with the values as such (because these are well within ranges seen over geological time scales of millions of years). The problem is with the rates of change of temperature and CO₂ ; specifically, how quickly those are changing in comparison with evolution of ecology.

So, rates of change in baseline (average) temperature, pCO₂ and ocean pH, are much faster than has occurred before. The conditions are also moving into extremes in the context of the era of human evolution and existence, and also extremes for the ecology of life on which we depend for food, resources and wellbeing.

Class Activity

The significance of human activity in releasing CO₂ from the burning of fossil fuels on the increase in atmospheric pCO₂ over the recent decades is accepted by most scientists. However, the topic remains a subject of active popular debate. Part of that debate centres on how CO₂ levels have changed throughout the history of Earth, while life evolved.

Discuss how life changed Earth from its appearance over 2 billion years ago, and what the implications would have been for early life forms in the changes in atmospheric CO₂ and O₂. What have been the implications for the formation of limestone on atmospheric CO₂, and what has human activity been doing to planet-scale ecology?

These are very wide ranging topics but for context:

- Ancestral life forms were strict anaerobes, which are killed by O₂.
- Over billions of years, photosynthesis has removed atmospheric CO₂, and replaced it with O₂.
- About half of the photosynthesis was performed by the microscopic plankton in the ocean. A small, but important, fraction of the atmospheric CO₂ removed during photosynthesis became locked away as what we term ‘fossil fuels’.
- Limestones were made mainly by plankton (see **Fig.1**), as skeletons that became buried, and these rocks lock-up CO₂ (we do not burn limestone, like we do fossil fuels, for example).
- Humans, and the ecology we depend upon, evolved in a low CO₂ atmosphere.
- The amount of fossil fuels combusted each year by humans equates to about 100 years’ worth of plankton photosynthesis. This is releasing CO₂ into the atmosphere.
- It is not plausible that the burning of fossil fuels could significantly diminish atmospheric O₂ levels. Humans are not going to run out of atmospheric O₂.

Units of CO₂ concentration

The concentration of gasses, and the proportions of gasses, is reported in different ways in the literature. However, the form in which it is most commonly reported in connection with CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere is in terms of parts per million (**ppm**).

Expressed as a % contribution, **1 ppm is 0.0001%**; **1% = 10000 ppm**.

If we consider a volume of gas of 1L, then a millionth of that volume is 10⁻⁶ L, which is 1 μL (which is the volume occupied by 1 mm³, so there are 10×10×10 (mm³) = 1000 μL in 1 mL).

If you consider a volume of gas of 1 m³, a millionth of that volume is 1 mL. So, 1 m³ of air contains, at 430 ppm CO₂, 430 mL of CO₂. That volume is similar to that of a drinks can.

Pre-industrial pCO₂ concentrations were around 260-270 ppm. The current (as of 2026) value is ca. 430 ppm. **The difference between the current pCO₂ and pre-industrial levels is primarily due to human activity burning fossil fuels, resulting in the release of CO₂.**

In a cubic metre of air, ca. 160 mL equates to the CO₂ added by human activity.

Changes in atmospheric CO₂ and the Keeling curve

The Keeling curve describes changes in atmospheric CO₂ over time, expressed as pCO₂. It is named after scientist Charles Keeling, who started the regular monitoring of this gas from 1958 at the Mauna Loa Observatory on Hawaii in the Pacific. The same generic term is now used to extend the description back in geological time.

The value of atmospheric pCO₂ varies with the seasons, declining when production (which consumes CO₂) is maximum in the land-mass dominated northern hemisphere (early summer to autumn), and increasing from autumn to late spring when the system is dominated by decay. This can be seen in **Fig.3**, as can changes in pCO₂ over the past 70 million years.

About 30% of the CO₂ released by human activity (in essence, the burning of fossil fuels) into the atmosphere is absorbed into the ocean.

Fig.3 Screenshot of the Keeling curve (available from <https://keelingcurve.ucsd.edu/>), of the atmospheric concentration of pCO₂ by the end of September 2025 (upper), and over the past 70 million years (lower). Values from before 0.8 million years ago are estimated from indirect measurements, while more recent values are from bubbles of air trapped in ice cores, and from 1958 directly from analysis of the atmosphere at Mauna Loa (Pacific). Note that the current pCO₂ value is higher than it has been for the past 1 million years (visible at the extreme right bottom of the lower plot).

Gas exchange between the atmosphere and ocean

Gasses exchange between the atmosphere and water occurs through a process that achieves an equilibrium, where the partial pressures of a gas on both sides are equal. If there are increases or decreases in concentrations in either the atmosphere or the water, it can take some time for that equilibrium to be re-established. Re-equilibration occurs more rapidly if there is mixing in the air and especially in the water column, and if there are flows of wind and/or water across the air-water interface.

Most gasses enter from the atmosphere into water and remain recognisably as the same chemical; for example, O₂ in water is still present as O₂. CO₂ is different: it dissolves into water to form a weak acid (carbonic acid) and that, in turn, forms other chemicals (carbonates and bicarbonates).

The collective term for the sum of all the types of inorganic C present in water is –

Dissolved Inorganic Carbon or DIC.

The actual amount of CO₂ dissolved in water that is present as CO₂ (what we term aqueous CO₂, or CO₂(aq) for short), is a very small part of all forms of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC). We will consider this further below (see [CARBONATE SYSTEM AND THE BUFFERING OF OCEAN pH](#)).

It is important to note that the value of pCO₂ in the air equilibrates with pCO₂(aq), but CO₂(aq) interacts to form other chemicals and affects the acidity of the water. This means that in the geological past (many millions of years ago), when atmospheric pCO₂ was high, so too was pCO₂(aq), and so the water of the ocean was also more acidic than it is now.

The current pH of the ocean is not, in itself, so much of a problem (though it may be for certain species). The ocean has been far more acidic in the distant past. The problem is more associated with the rate of acidification compared with the rate of evolution of the organisms to optimise growth at that pH. As we will see, there is an allied problem relating to changes in the buffering capacity of the carbonate system.

The pH of the ocean changes as :

- organisms use CO₂ in photosynthesis (pCO₂(aq)↓, pH↑, CO₂ may be absorbed from the atmosphere)

and/or

- as they release CO₂ during respiration (pCO₂(aq)↑, pH↓, CO₂ may be released into the atmosphere).

Temperature affects the solubility and partitioning of gasses between water and the atmosphere. That is true for CO₂ even though the concentration of CO₂(aq) is only a small component of the total DIC. With elevated water temperatures during what are termed ‘marine heatwaves’, the entry of CO₂ into the water is slowed and even reversed, with CO₂ coming back into the atmosphere (Müller et al. 2025). The same elevated temperatures may also increase the rates of biological activity, especially of respiration, leading to increased pCO₂(aq), a lower pH, and a greater likelihood of CO₂ being released.

You will explore these interactions later, using simulations.

WHERE DID ALL THE CO₂ GO?

Summary

- Most of the CO₂ originally in the atmosphere ended up in limestones (ca. 70%), and most of that (ca. 80%) is a product of biological activity in the construction of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) skeletons.
- Most of the remaining CO₂ was fixed by photosynthesis performed by microalgae and higher plants. A proportion of this fixed carbon is today present as what humans view as potential fossil fuels (petrochemicals - natural gas, oil, coal).
- While the carbon in limestone is effectively locked away from re-entering the atmosphere, that which is in petrochemicals is released back into the atmosphere as CO₂ when humans burn the gas, oil or coal.

If the early Earth atmosphere was more like that of modern-day Venus, with a very high pCO₂, where did Earth's atmospheric CO₂ go?

Most of it, ca. 70%, is thought to now reside in limestone. That material is predominately (ca. 80%) of biological origin, as the calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) parts of plankton and other mainly marine organisms. The biological material was also mainly deposited in more productive shallow waters. Calcium carbonate is soluble in seawater, especially under pressure at depth, but also at higher temperatures and at higher acidity.

Calcium carbonate can form two crystal structures: aragonite and calcite. Aragonite is more acid-soluble but forms more readily when seawater contains more magnesium. The effects that ocean acidification have on the dissolving of the CaCO₃ skeletons of marine organisms is not straightforward. These body parts are not built of pure aragonite and/or calcite but are involved with biological material that, at least in living organisms, shields much of the CaCO₃ from dissolution. The acidity that inevitably develops in marine sediments during the release of CO₂ during respiration and organic matter mineralisation, far exceeds that from ocean acidification.

A common focus for concerns of the effects of ocean acidification on marine organisms focusses on pteropods, a group of planktonic molluscs. While these organisms evolved during times of high pCO₂, this should not be taken to assume that the current species, which have evolved for life at low pCO₂, would not be placed at risk with ocean acidification (Peijnenburg et al. 2020).

Fig.4 Calcified plankton. Panels (a) and (b) are of the coccolithophorid *Emiliania huxleyi*, a single-celled microalgae that produces plates of calcium carbonate, coccoliths. Panel (a) shows many cells with separated coccoliths viewed under a standard light microscope; the scale bar is of 50µm, which is 0.05mm. Panel (b) is of a single cell, viewed under an electron microscope, showing the delicate structure of the chalk (CaCO_3) coccoliths that cover the cell, also with some separate coccoliths; the scale bar is 1µm, which is 0.001mm. The biological purpose of the coccoliths (which are made inside the cell and then extruded) remains unclear, but they accumulate on the sea floor in shallow waters and comprise the base material for many limestones. Fig.1 shows a satellite image of a bloom of this organism. Panel (c) shows a pteropod, one of many planktonic snails and sea-slugs <1cm long. They swim by beating their modified foot. The swirl of the shell is visible; there is evidence that under ocean acidification the calcification forming the shell is weakening (Bednaršek et al. 2012). Images courtesy of Claire Widdicombe, Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

Limestones in general, though subjected to weathering and other geological impacts, are relatively inert, especially when compared to the other primary fate of atmospheric CO_2 , which is incorporation into hydrocarbons. Those hydrocarbons are the products of primary production (i.e., ultimately photosynthetic fixation of CO_2) and transformations of that material into what humans exploit as petrochemicals (oil and gas from plankton, and coal from higher plants). Although some of these organic materials may leak into the atmosphere (notably as the gas methane, CH_4 , which is itself a potent greenhouse gas), the greater concern is with the extraction and burning of petrochemicals to support human needs. Such processes release, amongst other chemicals, CO_2 into the atmosphere. Plastics are also made from petrochemicals and ultimately these are either burnt, or digested by bacteria, both of which release CO_2 .

CARBONATE SYSTEM & THE BUFFERING OF OCEAN pH

Summary

- CO_2 from the atmosphere dissolves in water to give a weak acid (carbonic acid, H_2CO_3) which dissociates to bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) and carbonate ions (CO_3^{2-}). Collectively, this is called the carbonate system.
- The carbonate system provides seawater with a pH buffer, resisting changes in pH due to small additions or removals of protons. This helps to provide pH stability for the evolution of organisms affected by changes in pH (most notably the microplankton).
- With increased atmospheric CO_2 , the pH of seawater is decreasing to below the optimal buffering capacity of the carbonate buffer; not only is the ocean being acidified but its ability to resist further acidification is being decreased.
- Biological activity changes seawater pH because photosynthesis removes CO_2 (pH increases), while respiration adds CO_2 (pH decreases). These activities cause cyclic changes in the pH of seawater that far exceed the long-term average changes with ocean acidification.

Earth originally had an atmosphere more closely aligned with that of modern-day Venus, containing a very high atmospheric concentration of CO_2 , and little if any free O_2 . CO_2 is soluble in water, so as the early oceans formed, some of the atmospheric CO_2 dissolved into it.

CO_2 dissolves in water to give a weakly acidic solution, which then dissociates (splits, converts) into different ionic forms. These different ionic forms, together with $\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})$, are collectively termed '**dissolved inorganic carbon**', or **DIC**.

The inter-relationships between forms of DIC are shown in **Fig.5**. The balance between different forms of DIC at different pH values is shown in **Fig.6**.

Fig.5 Dissolution of CO_2 from the atmosphere into different forms of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) that collectively comprise the carbonate system. Note the connections are all marked with double-ended arrows; this is because the concentration of each component is in equilibrium with all the others. If there is a change in the atmospheric CO_2 , then this will alter the total DIC concentration and work its way through to affect the amount of H^+ (i.e., changing $[\text{H}^+]$) and thence alters the acidity of the water.

Fig.6 Ratios of different components of DIC (as % of total) with pH. These are shown for 20°C and salinity of 30. Also indicated is the typical pH range of seawater taking into account biological activity; this is expected to shift to the left with ocean acidification. At lower temperature and/or salinity, the curves shift to the right. The region of maximum buffering capacity in seawater (dominated by the equilibrium of the carbonate system; **Fig.5**) is around pH 8. Ocean acidification is shifting the baseline pH down closer to pH8.

Because biological activity adds and removes CO_2 , it affects pH. With photosynthesis, CO_2 is removed and pH increases. With respiration, CO_2 is added and pH decreases. These effects, occurring over day-night cycles, or with the growth and then decay of microalgal blooms, can generate changes in seawater pH that far exceed the long-term average change in pH linked to the increase in atmospheric pCO_2 .

From **Fig.5**, it will be apparent that as the amount of CO_2 in the atmosphere increases, so more will dissolve in the water, and the acidity of that water will increase (pH will decrease). Importantly, this also shifts the balance of the components of DIC (**Fig.6**) and alters the buffering capacity of the system.

The early Earth ocean (approximately 3-4 billion years ago) was slightly acidic due to high atmospheric CO_2 , with pH range from 6.0 to 7.5. The weathering of rocks released ions such as calcium (Ca^{2+}) into the ocean. These ions reacted with bicarbonate ions to form calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), gradually raising the pH toward slightly alkaline values (around pH 8). This shifted pH to neutral, and then to alkaline conditions that would have been more favourable for the evolution of life.

As life on Earth evolved, a major change occurred to dominance of life forms, that really developed from around 1.85 billion years ago. That change was the progressive success of photosynthetic organisms that exploit sunlight and CO_2 to grow and produce O_2 as a byproduct. The atmosphere progressively changed from containing high levels of CO_2 and vanishingly little O_2 , to that which has been dominant over the period in which humans have evolved, which has very little CO_2 and a lot of O_2 (noting that the major gas in the atmosphere is nitrogen, N_2). Over this period, the DIC content, DIC composition, and

the acidity of the oceans changed; the modern ocean is mildly alkaline. The lower panel in **Fig.3** shows how $p\text{CO}_2$ has changed over the last 70 million years.

The chemical equilibria of the carbonate system, with the bidirectional transformation between ionic forms of the dissociated weak acid – carbonic acid (H_2CO_3), functions as a buffer.

What is a ‘buffer’? A buffer is a solution that resists changes in pH when small amounts of acid (H^+) or alkali (OH^-) are added. In seawater, the carbonate system acts as a buffer. The system contains three interconvertible forms – carbonic acid, bicarbonate (HCO_3^-), and carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) - that can absorb or release H^+ ions through the dissociation reactions shown in **Fig.5**. When acid is added, the equilibrium shifts to absorb the additional H^+ ; when alkali is added, the system releases H^+ to react with the added OH^- to compensate. This interconversion between forms of dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) dampens pH changes.

If you add even a tiny amount of acid or alkali to pure water, the pH changes very quickly and dramatically - by several pH units. In contrast, seawater, with its carbonate buffer, shows only a modest change in pH under the same additions of acid or alkali. This is explored in the ‘**Class activity**’ in the section on **ACIDITY**.

If the seawater system is open to the atmosphere, excess CO_2 can be released to the air when the pH decreases because more DIC is present as CO_2 (**Fig.6**). Conversely, if atmospheric CO_2 increases, more CO_2 dissolves in the water (increasing $p\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})$), which shifts the equilibrium to produce more H^+ so pH decreases - but that change will be limited because of the buffering interactions.

The functioning of the carbonate buffer becomes apparent in practice when you try to alter the pH of seawater by adding drops of acid or alkali (e.g., HCl or NaOH); it takes some time for the pH probe to provide a stable response because the buffer system is actively resisting the change.

There is a catch, however, with all buffers: they work most effectively only within a specific pH range. For the carbonate system in seawater, that range is approximately pH 8.1-8.3. As **Fig.6** shows, this zone corresponds to a marked transition in the distribution of DIC types. For example, as pH decreases, so the proportion present as carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) decreases sharply while that as CO_2 increases. As pH increases above pH 8, the proportion as HCO_3^- decreases and that as CO_2 drops to very low values, while that as CO_3^{2-} increases. Outside this optimal range, the same concentration of added H^+ or OH^- will cause a much larger shift in pH – the buffer becomes less effective.

The ability of the ocean to resist changes in acidity is quantified by the **Revelle factor** (discussed in detail by Egleston et al. 2010). **A higher Revelle factor indicates lower buffering capacity.** Critically, the Revelle factor is projected to increase as ocean pH drops, and the effect is more pronounced at the poles than in the tropics (Jiang et al. 2019).

A crucial take-home message is this:

As atmospheric CO_2 increases and drives ocean acidification, the pH of seawater is shifting progressively below the optimal buffering range of the carbonate system.

This means the ocean's chemical stability, its ability to resist further pH changes, is declining. For marine organisms that depend on stable seawater chemistry for growth and calcification, this weakening of the buffering capacity has serious ecological implications.

Salinity also affects pH, though the interactions are complex depending on whether the freshwater source contains much carbonate (i.e., how ‘hard’ is the water). If the freshwater is soft (low carbonate content) then the effect of decreasing salinity (i.e., decreasing NaCl etc.) is associated also with a

decrease in the components of the carbonate system. This thus radically decreases the buffering capacity of the water.

Modelling Activity – Appendix 1, Experiment 1

In Appendix 1 you will find an activity, **EXPERIMENT 1**, with which to explore changes in the carbonate system with $p\text{CO}_2$ and pH.

This work makes use of a simulation model that operates on MS Windows.

ALKALINITY & ALKALINISATION

Summary

- The addition of negatively charged ions such as carbonate (CO_3^-) or silicate (SiO_4^{4-}) increases alkalinity and thus raises pH.
- Such additions of alkalinity on a massive scale have potential to provide a means to counter ocean acidification through a process termed alkalinisation.
- Changes in concentrations of nutrient ions (nitrate, phosphate, ammonium) also affect pH in different ways through increasing (or decreasing for ammonium) alkalinity.

Alkalinity

There is another factor that is often mentioned when considering seawater pH, and that is **alkalinity**.

Alkalinity affects the strength of the buffering system that resists changes in pH. These contributors are ions that can neutralise added acid (i.e., accept H^+ ions). In seawater the major contributors to alkalinity are the negatively charged components of the carbonate system, namely CO_3^- and HCO_3^- . Borate is also a significant contributor to alkalinity in seawater.

There are other ions that also have minor impacts on alkalinity, which are affected by biological activity. The removal or addition of nitrate (NO_3^-), phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) and ammonium (NH_4^+) into seawater all affect alkalinity and coupled with the associated physiological reactions, also affect pH.

Table 1 Affects on acidity of addition and removal of ions of importance to biological processes. Removal is associated with biological production (e.g., growth of microalgae), while addition is associated with consumption and decay. The ratios of additions and removals will govern the total ecologically-related pH change.

Molecule	Effect on acidity on removal	Effect on acidity on addition
CO_2	Decrease (pH \uparrow)	Increase (pH \downarrow)
NH_4^+	Increase (pH \downarrow)	Decrease (pH \uparrow)
NO_3^-	Decrease (pH \uparrow)	Increase (pH \downarrow)
PO_4^{3-}	Decrease (pH \uparrow)	Increase (pH \downarrow)
Ca^{++}	Increase (pH \downarrow)	Decrease (pH \uparrow)

pH increases slightly when NO_3^- and/or PO_4^{3-} are consumed (removed by growth coupled with photosynthesis), and when NH_4^+ is released (which occurs during the consumption of biomass by bacteria and animals). These changes are overshadowed by the consequences of removing CO_2 (i.e. photosynthesis, which causes pH to increase) or adding CO_2 (i.e., respiration, which decreases pH).

Biology plays an important role in altering alkalinity through the process of calcification. This will be described in the section on **PHYSIOLOGICAL PROCESSES & OCEAN ACIDIFICATION**.

Alkalinisation to counter OA

It has been proposed that humans could seek to counter ocean acidification through increasing the alkalinity of the sea. To exploit this process of alkalinization, requires either adding minerals or through electrolysis. The former involves the deposition of large amounts of minerals such as silicates or carbonates. These minerals have to be mined, ground to fine dust and then dissolved into the seawater. Electrolysis would require a vast amount of electricity, which would have to be generated by nuclear or sustainable means (solar, wind, tide).

If we consider the use of limestone, CaCO_3 , then to counter the consequences of 1 tonne of CO_2 dissolving into seawater requires the dissolution of 1.5-2 tonnes of limestone. From this, it can be estimated that something like 16 times the current global production of limestone would be required to compensate for the yearly production of CO_2 through human activity.

Class Activity

Assuming that you need 2 tonnes of limestone to compensate for the acidity increase due to 1 tonne of CO_2 dissolving into seawater, how many tonnes of limestone would be required to compensate for the consumption of a tank of fuel in a typical petrol-powered car?

For context, consider that 1 tonne of CO_2 is the product of burning approximately 430L of petrol. Assume a fuel tank capacity of 50 L.

What caveats do you place on your calculations? What alternative ways of achieving the same aim (alleviating further increases in ocean acidification) could you use?

Discuss also the implications of using biofuels, or battery power (remember where the metals come from for the batteries, and that electric vehicles are heavier, needing more raw material etc.).

Further insight on the topic may be gained by asking an AI site the following question:

How much rock is required to be added to seawater to compensate for the alkalinity changes from 1 tonne of CO_2 ?

As with all usages of an AI, be careful to check the information provided, including any calculations.

Modelling Activity – Appendix 1, Experiment 2

In Appendix 1 you will find an activity, **EXPERIMENT 2**, with which to explore changes in acidity due to calcification and alkalinisation. This experiment merges concepts in both this and the following sections.

This work makes use of a simulation model that operates on MS Windows.

PHYSIOLOGICAL PROCESSES & OCEAN ACIDIFICATION

Summary

- Biological activity affects water pH. The growth of microalgae increases pH. The growth of organisms that consume microalgae or other consumers, or that degrades detritus (i.e., decay), decreases pH.
- All organisms have an optimal range of pH that enables their growth. Too high, or too low, and the organisms will be subjected to stress and eventually die. This is especially a problem for microorganisms because their entire cell surface is in contact with water.
- Ocean acidification, the lowering of pH and a weakening of the buffering capacity, has scope to alter the competitive advantage of different plankton species. Larger microplankton also experiences larger changes in pH over the day, between photosynthesis in the light (pH increases) and respiring at night (pH decreases).
- High rates of microalgal growth can increase the pH to lethal levels. This may be more likely to develop with ocean acidification as the starting pH is lower allowing a longer period of biomass development. In extreme instances this could enable the growth of larger blooms, followed by death and decay with enhanced risks of deoxygenation.
- Effects of ocean acidification on plankton animals (zooplankton) are inconclusive, but juvenile stages are likely most at risk both directly (because being smaller they are more affected by external pH) and indirectly (because they are more susceptible to changes in their diet, and pH affects microalgal growth).
- Calcification, the removal of CaCO_3 by organisms, results in a decrease in pH. The reason that limestone formation over millions of years did not result in an acidic ocean is because of weathering that brought in other ions, and also because of the gradual decrease in atmospheric pCO_2 .

Photosynthesis and the growth of phototrophs

Photosynthesis requires light and CO_2 . The core enzyme for photosynthesis is RuBisCO (in full, the enzyme name is 'ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase'), which uses CO_2 as its substrate for C-fixation. However, marine organisms face a challenge: they can access either dissolved $\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})$ or the far more abundant bicarbonate ion (HCO_3^-) present in seawater (see [Fig.6](#)). If they use HCO_3^- they must use another enzyme first, carbonic anhydrase, to convert HCO_3^- into CO_2 . (As an aside, humans have the same enzyme, used to convert HCO_3^- in our blood to CO_2 which we then exhale.)

Through the removal of either CO_2 or HCO_3^- , with the re-equilibration of the carbonate system ([Figs. 5 & 6](#)), photosynthesis leads to the removal of CO_2 and therefore to an increase in pH (i.e. a decrease in acidity).

Phototrophs (i.e., photosynthesising organisms), such as microalgae, also require other nutrients. The major requirements are for nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P), and for certain microalgae also for calcium (Ca). These are obtained typically through the uptake of nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+), phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) and calcium (Ca^{++}). From the section on [Alkalinity](#) (above, [Table 1](#)), it will be noted that the uptake of these ions will affect alkalinity and thus have an additional, though relatively minor, impact on pH. So, growth of microalgae using ammonium results in a smaller increase in pH; similarly, Ca^{++} removal for calcification (forming chalky plates, see [Fig.4](#)) also dampens the pH rise, or could even reverse it, increasing acidity.

At lower rates of growth, and/or with high rates of gas exchange between the atmosphere and sea surface, changes in pH will be decreased. In calm warm conditions, and with high nutrient loads, however, there is potential for microalgal photosynthesis to significantly elevate the pH. At extremes, with eutrophication, this could be lethal, resulting in the death of the microalgae. Under ocean acidification, this whole complex process commences at a lower pH, potentially enabling larger microalgal blooms to develop in eutrophic waters.

Respiration and the growth of consumers

Consumers, as well as the activity of microalgae in darkness, release CO₂ but consumers also release NH₄⁺ and PO₄³⁻ (Table 1). The net effect is the decrease in pH. This decrease is especially rapid in waters with high rates of decay. While photosynthesis (which raises pH) is rather a slow process as it is limited by light, decay can proceed more rapidly with the sinking of detritus.

Acidification occurs in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions, but is faster and greater in aerobic conditions (i.e., where oxygen is readily available). This is because aerobic conditions enable faster decay rates and the end product is CO₂ (which acidifies water) rather than intermediaries such as lactic acid (which, while acidic, is only a partial decay product) or methane (which does not affect acidity, though it is a potent green-house gas).

Acidification during respiration will lower the pH even further when starting in conditions of low pH (i.e., under ocean acidification). In addition, because the buffering capacity of the water is less under ocean acidification, the decrease in pH will be more rapid.

Recall that the problem with ocean acidification is not so much with the pH (in the past the ocean has been more acidic than they are currently) but with the potential rate of change of pH due to a lessening of the buffer capacity. That accelerating rate of change may be increased again if elevated temperatures increase biological activity that also affects pH.

There are few studies of the impacts of pH upon metazoan (animal) zooplankton. These animals are key in the food webs that support fisheries and whales, as intermediaries from the microalgal production. A study of the effects on the life cycle of a small copepod indicated that the earliest stages of development, but also the male adults, were most affected; the larger adult females seemed less effected (Cripps et al. 2014). Part of this impact may be indirect, through changes in the quality of prey and also with the efficiency of digestion of that prey. Collectively these factors will affect the efficiency with which food is converted into animal biomass (Cripps et al. 2016). For a small animal, such as a juvenile copepod (length <0.1mm), the pH within the gut would be strongly affected by the pH of the surrounding water. There are various digestive enzymes in these animals, but at least some of them have alkaline optimum pH values (Freese et al. 2012). If the external pH is lower, then one might expect that the gut pH would also be decreased and potentially adversely affect the efficiency of digestion. This suggestion is consistent with the work of Tang et al. (2011), that larger copepod stages have digestive enzymes optimised for more acidic conditions within the gut.

Calcification and pH

It may be thought that the removal of CO₂ through the formation of CaCO₃ by marine organisms, which ultimately locks C away as limestone, would counter ocean acidification. After all, if adding CO₂ decreases pH, surely removal of CO₂ through this process would increase pH?

Actually, the opposite is true. **Calcification contributes to acidification, decreasing pH.**

To understand why, you need to recall the roles of the carbonate ion (CO_3^{2-}) and calcium ion (Ca^{++}) in alkalinity. Adding CO_3^{2-} raises alkalinity so pH increases; removing it decreases pH. Hence, **calcification increased acidification**. For microalgae that make chalky plates (the coccolithophores; **Figs. 1 & 4**) that production of CaCO_3 plates and the decrease in pH compensate partly (and potentially completely) for the pH increase that occurs with their photosynthesis (Flynn et al. 2016). For animals, however, the decrease in pH supported by calcification is added to that from their respiration (which produces CO_2); see **Table 1**.

The follow-on question is then why the formation of limestone, over geological time, did not result in an acidic ocean ($\text{pH} < 7$), rather the current ocean which is basic (alkaline, $\text{pH} > 7$)?

The answer is because weathering of rocks brings ions into the ocean that increase alkalinity (pH increases). Coupled with the decreasing atmospheric pCO_2 (because of the gradual drawdown, conversion, of atmospheric CO_2 into limestone) that decreases the acidification, this has over geological time spans resulted in an ocean with a basic pH.

The current ocean acidification is occurring because more CO_2 is entering the atmosphere, so more is entering the ocean, thus causing a pH decrease at a faster rate than rock weathering can counteract it with alkalisation. The suggestion to artificially enhance alkalisation (see **ALKALINITY & ALKALINISATION**, above) is born from an idea to replicate a faster natural weathering of rocks.

Class Activity

This activity provides a preamble, introduction, to the modelling activity described below, and also leading into the next section on **ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONING**.

It may be helpful to first explore the subject of eutrophication –

Flynn, K. J. (2024). Exploring eutrophication – polluting with too much of a good thing; a teaching guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12529789>

Draw out a simple conceptual food web with nutrients, microalgae and zooplankton in a water column, with gas exchange at the surface. Draw also a sketch graph of how you think those nutrients, microalgae and zooplankton concentrations and abundances would change over time. What you should produce will show a sequence of nutrients supporting growth of the microalgae, which will then be eaten by the increasing (growing) zooplankton population, which will in turn release nutrients as waste products to go back around the food web.

Now draw in the consequences of the addition of nutrients to the food web (for example via eutrophication), and also another graph that considers how different processes in the development and collapse of a plankton bloom may affect the pH.

Repeat this considering a low-nutrient system (which typically goes to steady-state rather than a more typical bloom event).

And now, reconsider the above in the context of acidified ocean, where pH starts at a lower level and, because the buffering is weaker, the pH can oscillate more in consequence of the same biological activities.

You will test your conclusions in the next section, **ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONING**.

Modelling Activity – Appendix 1, Experiment 2

In Appendix 1 you will find an activity, **EXPERIMENT 2**, with which to explore changes in acidity due to calcification and alkalization, and also the consequences of production and consumption. This experiment merges concepts in both this and the previous sections.

This work makes use of a simulation model that operates on MS Windows.

ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONING

Summary

- Organisms of different sizes and growth rates are directly affected by changes in pH in different ways. Smaller organisms experience pH changes closely aligned with that in the bulk water surrounding them; larger organisms experience more extreme changes due to the thicker boundary-layer that delays chemical interactions with the bulk water.
- Food webs in marine systems are driven by the activity of microbes. While microbes are directly exposed to pH effects, larger organisms (at higher trophic levels) are indirectly affected by any effects of ocean acidification on the microbes.
- Many marine animals have microplanktonic juvenile stages that, like all juveniles, tend to have more specific demands for nutrition than do adults. The success of reproduction for most marine animals will likely be directly or indirectly affected by ocean acidification acting upon juvenile stages.
- The complexity of all the ecosystem interactions means that attributing a specific risk to ocean acidification remains very difficult.

Organism size (allometry)

What matters for the individual organism is the pH (technically, the concentration of protons, $[H^+]$) at the cell surface, where nutrient uptake, ion transport and pH-sensitive enzymatic processes occur. This is most important for the unicellular microbes that drive production in the Ocean.

Each organism is surrounded by a zone of water that is undisturbed by the turbulence of swimming or sinking; this is called the **boundary layer**. The passage of chemicals by diffusion within the boundary layer is slower than outside of it. The differences between the concentrations of chemicals used or produced by an organism next to its cell surface and that in the water outside of the boundary layer (in the **bulk water**) are functions of:

- organism size; larger organisms have a thicker boundary layer
- the rate of chemical uptake or release; faster growing organisms have greater differences in concentrations of chemicals between their cell surface and the bulk water.

Various processes affect the transfer of protons (H^+) in and out of an organism. This means that pH changes next to the cell are greater than in the bulk water outside of the boundary layer.

It is very difficult to measure chemical concentrations in the boundary layer. This layer is often only a fraction of a μm thick (**1000 $\mu m = 1 mm$**). Although it is possible to insert a pH probe into this layer for some organisms, scientists typically use mathematics to calculate concentrations based on diffusion rates and biological rates of uptake or release.

The research shows us that:

- Small marine plankton (less than $5\mu m$) have such thin boundary layers that conditions next to their cells are similar to those in the bulk water.
- Larger, especially fast-growing non-motile, marine plankton, experience conditions next to their cells that can differ significantly from those in the bulk water.

What does this mean for the impacts of ocean acidification? Smaller organisms are more directly exposed to fluctuations in bulk water pH, as their thin boundary layer provide no buffering. Larger organisms typically experience modified conditions within their boundary layers, and these can be more

extreme than those experienced by small organisms. With ocean acidification, as the carbonate buffer becomes weaker, the ability of bulk seawater to dampen pH changes decreases. This means that metabolically driven pH shifts in the boundary layer of larger organisms will be even more pronounced.

We thus expect larger planktonic microbes to experience greater fluctuation in pH ($[H^+]$) at their cell surfaces with ocean acidification. All else considered equal, we expect ocean acidification to be more detrimental to larger microalgae. You can read more about this in Flynn et al. (2012).

Why does this matter? Organism size affects crucial processes, such as competition for nutrient uptake, predator-prey interactions, sinking rates, and susceptibility to viral infection.

Differential impacts of ocean acidification by size will reshape plankton community structure and the dynamics of marine food web.

Direct and indirect effects

Set against the natural variability of pH over the course of each day (\uparrow in the light, \downarrow in the dark) and the dynamics of plankton blooms as they grow (pH \uparrow) and decay (pH \downarrow), ocean acidification recasts these events to a lower baseline pH. As the buffering capacity of the carbonate system is lower, these increases and decreases occurring concurrent with a given level of biological activity can be more extreme.

A major challenge for ocean acidification research is determining the direct effects on specific components of an ecosystem and whether such effects then indirectly impact other components of the food web. It is most likely that direct effects are limited to planktonic members of the food web. However, most marine organisms have planktonic juvenile stages; this applies to many fish species, which produce eggs and spend the very first stages of their life as plankton, critically dependant on the availability of other plankton (and often specific types of plankton) as food.

Studying the effects of ocean acidification on a particular species while providing it with optimal prey as food in an experiment can not replicate real conditions that would see the prey also affected by ocean acidification. In addition, microbes evolve over time. There will be 'winners' and 'losers' but we do not know how the whole marine ecosystem will respond to combinations of OA with temperature, pollution and fishing.

Different regions of the ocean can be susceptible to ocean acidification to a different degree, reflecting how circulation moves and redistributes water that has previously been exposed to elevated atmospheric CO_2 . A well-researched example is in Puget Sound off northwest America (US state of Washington), where ocean acidification has been identified not only as a cause for weakened shellfish production, but also as having potential adverse impacts on organisms not directly affected by changes in pH, such as finfish (Haigh et al. 2015).

Diatoms are important microalgae supporting many food webs. Their unique feature is making their glass-like cell walls ('frustules'), out of silica. They make these cell walls by taking up dissolved silicate from the seawater. The use of silicate by diatoms does not affect pH, but a decrease in pH negatively affects the rate of silica dissolution in the cell walls of dead diatoms. This has implications for the sinking of these diatoms (the silicate cell walls make them heavier), and also for the return of silicate back to surface waters to sustain the future growths of diatoms. If the frustules sink to greater depths before dissolving, the return of the soluble silicate will be slower, potentially limiting subsequent diatom growth.

Nitrification

Another indirect effect of ocean acidification upon the wider food web, is via its impact on a process called **nitrification**. This is important because the product of nitrification is nitrate, which is the most important form of N-nutrient used by marine microalgae.

Most marine animals and other consumers produce their waste nitrogen in the form of ammonium (in contrast, humans produce urine as the N-waste product). In fact, this N is present in two forms, as ammonium and ammonia, that is as NH_4^+ and NH_3 , respectively. The higher the seawater pH, the greater the proportion present as ammonia (NH_3).

In the depths of the ocean, bacteria are so lacking in carbon that some of them fix CO_2 by using energy obtained from oxidising ammonia (NH_3) through to nitrite (NO_2^-) and then to nitrate (NO_3^-). These bacteria are called **nitrifiers** because they collectively produce nitrate. Unlike photosynthesis, this is a form of C-fixation that occurs in darkness.

There are two interesting features of the interaction with pH.

- i) As with photosynthesis, C-fixation with nitrification results in a decrease in acidity (pH increases). This occurs because CO_2 is removed. That is important for nitrifiers because, as the pH increases so does the proportion present as NH_3 , which is the substrate for nitrification. There is thus a positive feedback.
- ii) With ocean acidification, the proportion of ammonia+ammonium present as ammonia (NH_3) decreases. This is problematic because there is less substrate (NH_3) for nitrification. It has been calculated that ocean acidification will decrease production of nitrate by perhaps 1/3rd (Beman et al. 2011; Wannicke et al. 2018).

What happens to the ocean ecosystems if the rate of nitrification is decreased is unclear. While there may be less nitrate, ammonium is itself a good source of nitrogen for microalgae, although microalgae utilize ammonium and nitrate through different physiological pathways. Different microalgae species may either benefit or suffer, while the nutritional status of the microalgae as food for animals may also change. It is another example of how direct and indirect effects collectively cloud our understanding of the consequences of ocean acidification.

Class Activity

Draw out the life cycle of different marine animals, identifying especially the juvenile stages and what they feed upon.

From this, and for different age-stages, identify and draw out food webs involving the organisms that they feed upon. Which of these organisms (juveniles and prey) are microscopic (ca. <1mm)? Note that some smaller animals (such as copepods) may actually be smaller than the larger single-celled plankton!

Organisms smaller than ca. 0.5 mm are most likely to be directly affected by changes in seawater pH. From this, trace the potential impacts of ocean acidification through the food webs. Try and identify parts of the food web that are more likely to be directly or indirectly affected by ocean acidification.

Look at maps of ocean circulation and of fish migration; what other challenges can you find in trying to determine the risks presented by ocean acidification?

Modelling Activity – Appendix 1, Experiment 3

In Appendix 1 you will find an activity, **EXPERIMENT 3**, with which to explore interactions between changes in acidity and ecological functioning, including with calcification.

This makes use of a simulation model that operates on MS Windows.

OCEAN ACIDIFICATION – HOW DAMAGING IS IT?

As will now be apparent, the subject of ocean acidification, and its effects on ecology, are highly complex. At present, we do not know enough on what the overall effects will be, where they will be most severe and when (or if) they will occur.

What we currently know is:

- We lack sufficient information on how ecosystems function under changing baseline pH to fully understand how well different specific marine organisms will respond to ocean acidification. pH is never constant because ecosystem activity itself rapidly alters pH. How organisms respond to changes with ocean acidification may be related to the variability in pH they experience in their environment on a daily or weekly basis.
- The impact of ocean acidification on any individual organism may be direct (pH impact on physiology) and/or indirect (pH impact on a prey or predator, for example).
- Ocean acidification is not interacting in isolation from other impacts. It is occurring against a background of changes in temperature and resource availability. Ocean acidification is one of the components of what scientists term as ‘multi-stressors’.
- Multi-stressor interactions can often be synergistic; that is to say the interactions are not additive or linear, but multiplicative and non-linear. As an example of synergism, students and their teachers often experience such multi-stressor interactions during the first month of a new academic year; they bring together a wide range of air-borne diseases (cold, ‘flu, covid etc.) that can overwhelm the immune defences of an individual person. In a similar way, combinations of stresses (pH, temperature, hypoxia, resource availability, disease, predation) adversely affect marine organisms.
- Multi-stressor interactions are difficult to predict and at extremes can lead to ‘**regime shifts**’ - sudden changes in the functioning of the ecosystem. The conditions that promote such a change are termed ‘**tipping point**’ conditions. Ocean acidification may contribute to such events.
- Ocean acidification is a long-term and slow process. It is slow to develop, and even if we stopped adding CO₂ to the atmosphere today, it may take a long time for the effects of ocean acidification to subside. This is because of the time it takes water deep in the ocean to move around the Earth and reemerge at the surface affecting the plankton growths that drive most productivity. Moreover, the natural processes through which the background ocean pH increases (due to the input of chemicals that naturally cause alkalisation, from rock weathering, and due to the biological activity) will take perhaps 10,000’s of years to re-equilibrate.
- Against this background, organisms will continue to evolve, some faster than others. Whether they will be successful will depend on whether they are also able to overcome the pressures of other (multi-) stressors. The most benign situation for such evolution is thus the minimisation of the effects of other stressors, and the unaffected continuation of food supply. However, in reality that will not happen – some organisms will adapt more successfully than the others.

Class Activity

Have a class discussion about ocean acidification. Focus on the following questions:

How concerned should we be about ocean acidification, and why? Consider the following:

- given that pH varies with biological activity over a wider range than that caused by elevated atmospheric CO₂ dissolving into seawater, is there actually a problem of consequence, to be concerned about (recall the changes in buffering capacity and re-drawing of biological cycles at a lower pH baseline)
- direct and indirect effects – known and unknown impacts
- impacts on fisheries (important for food) vs impacts on specific locations (such as the Great Barrier Reef, with importance for biodiversity)

What can we do to prevent, or minimise, ocean acidification? Consider the following:

- a global problem but with causes mainly originating from certain countries (though note where most global imports of food and goods originate – many countries effectively export their CO₂ production by obtaining goods from other countries)
- the longevity of the events (10's to 100's of years due to ocean circulation)

What can we do to mitigate the effects of ocean acidification? Consider the following:

- identify multi-stressors which may exacerbate (complicate, amplify) the effects of ocean acidification (e.g., eutrophication, increasing temperature) – which of these may be acted upon, and how?
- alkalinisation; do you think the amounts of chemicals required make this a useful approach versus how much damage may be caused elsewhere (e.g. terrestrial rock mining) in using such methods; could it have local uses, such as near shellfish nurseries?

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Appendix 1 Simulating changes in seawater pH and interactions with biology

The following describes a series of experiments, conducted using simulation models.

These should be conducted in sequence so that understanding gained from one experiment is carried forwards to the next one.

The models are available as listed:

Experiment	Location	File name
Exp.1	Flynn, K. (2026). Effects of pCO ₂ and biological activity on seawater pH. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18456929	ProBleu OA Exp1 CP.sip
Exp.2	Flynn, K. J. (2026). Calcification and alkalinisation experiments. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18457112	ProBleu OA Exp2 CP.sip
Exp.3	Flynn, K. J. (2026). Ecological interactions with ocean acidification. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18457187	ProBleu OA Exp3 CP.sip

To run models, first if not yet installed, install Powersim 10 Studio Cockpit, then load the model

- The *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application works on PCs operating *Microsoft Windows*.
- Visit the *Powersim Studio* download site at <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>
- Download *Cockpit* (64-bit or 32-bit; most PCs will be 64-bit).
- Follow instructions provided by *Powersim* to install the software. (Accept default suggestions.)
- Download the model from the location indicated in the table above.
- To run a model, locate the file in your *MS Windows* file directory using *Explorer*.
- The file should have the *Powersim Studio 10* logo associated with it - clicking on the file name will open the file within the application.
- The model will open into a Home page; **follow the onscreen instructions and the suggestions given in the experiment descriptions.**

Each model has several pages, introducing the project, giving a brief summary and then the 'Explore' page from which you run the simulations. Switch between these pages by clicking on the buttons on the lefthand side.

It is recommended that you select 'Fit' from the magnification options so see the whole page contents.

EXPERIMENT 1: Effects of pCO₂ and biological activity on seawater pH

As illustrated in **Fig.5**, there are a series of complex interactions between the atmospheric concentration of CO₂ (pCO_{2atm}) and the carbonate system that plays an important role in buffering the pH of seawater. In addition, biological processes remove CO₂ (photosynthesis) and add CO₂ (respiration) to the seawater. These processes affect seawater pH, but the degree to which they do so depends on the balance of rates adding and removing CO₂ (both biological and via gas exchange between the air and water) and also on the buffering capacity of the carbonate system in cushioning changes in pH.

This model allows you to explore interactions between changes in the following upon seawater pH:

- atmospheric pCO₂
- water temperature
- wind speed (and thence gas exchange rates)
- biological removal (photosynthesis) or addition (respiration) of CO₂.

Collectively, these factors affect changes in seawater acidity, both with respect to the steady-state (equilibrium) value and the rate at which the system attains such a value.

In these experiments, using the model **ProBleu OA Exp1 CP.sip**, you can explore:

- effects on acidity of changing atmospheric pCO₂ (with and without changes in temperature)
- effects of acidity on the composition of DIC
- effects on acidity of changing biological production starting at different atmospheric pCO₂
- effects of the starting acidity value upon the rate of change in consequence of biological production

Note here that temperature (**Temp**) is only affecting the temperature of seawater and hence the carbonate chemistry. In reality, changing temperature would also affect the rate of organism growth that would consume and/or produce CO₂. Note also that the system may be closed to the atmosphere, so in reality the rates of change would be affected by gas exchange and thence re-equilibration of the carbonate chemistry (**Fig.5**).

Changes in acidity; how to interpret the value of $\delta[H^+]$

Acidity is described by the proton concentration, as $[H^+]$. Recall that pH is just a (negative log) transform of $[H^+]$ (**Fig.2**). Because pH is a log transform, it is inappropriate to refer to only changes in pH (such as increases or decreases in pH by 0.5) without referring to its original value. More usefully then, we should refer to changes in $[H^+]$. The mathematical symbol for changes over time, is the Greek lowercase letter, δ (delta). We thus refer to rates of change in acidity as $\delta[H^+]$. A positive value indicates acidity is increasing (pH↓); a negative value that acidity is decreasing (pH↓).

You may note that, under constant rates of addition or removal of CO₂, the value of $\delta[H^+]$ increases or decreases over time while the **pH** is changing. What this is telling you is that, for a given change in addition or removal of CO₂ the acidity is changing by a different amount because the acidity is moving out of (indicated by $\delta[H^+]$ increasing), or into (indicated by $\delta[H^+]$ decreasing) the zone of highest buffering capacity of the carbonate system.

Also, note that there are two plots of $\delta[H^+]$ against time, one of which ('**detailed scale**') gives detail for values for $\delta[H^+]$ between -5 to 5; use this detailed plot to help judge whether the system is at equilibrium with no change in pH, such that $\delta[H^+] = 0$. There is a thin black line at $\delta[H^+] = 0$, to help you judge this equilibrium point, and the current value is given in the box next to the graph.

The model interface

Below is a screenshot of the model interface, showing the 'Explore' page.

Fig.A1 Screenshot of an example from the *Explore* page of the model.

The image in **Fig.A1** is annotated to show the following:

- i) Buttons to control **pause** frequency (the simulation automatically pauses as required), **temperature**, and **wind** (0 isolates the water from the atmosphere).
- ii) Sliders to control **pCO₂atm** and **production** (+ve for photosynthesis, consuming CO₂, -ve for consumption with respiration, producing CO₂).
- iii) Graphs showing changes in temperature, wind, pCO₂atm and production over time; these provide you with a record of the changes made during the simulation.
- iv) Graphs showing pCO₂atm and current acidity
- v) Graphs showing changes in the carbonate chemistry vs pH and also changing over time.
- vi) Graphs showing changes in pH and acidity (i.e., [H⁺], nanomole H⁺ Kg⁻¹) changing over time, and also of pH vs acidity (note this is strongly curved as pH is a log transform of [H⁺]; **Fig.2c**).
- vii) Graphs showing changes in acidity, i.e., δ[H⁺]; the lefthand plot shows detail around δ[H⁺] = 0, with the black line following zero change. The current value is reported in the box.

NOTE: The **Wind** speed affects the rate at which the carbonate system reaches equilibrium, a status you can follow by the value of $\delta[\text{H}^+]$. For the studies detailed below, you may wish to set **Pause** at 10d if the equilibrium is slow, or use a **Pause** at 5d repeatedly, as required.

Explorations

Effects of altering atmospheric CO₂

For these studies, set **Production** = 0.

To start, set **Pause** = 5 d, **Wind** = 50 m/s, **Temperature** = 10°C.

Set **pCO₂atm** = 100 ppm, and run the model. The model will run for the first 5d, and automatically pause.

Now change **pCO₂atm** to 200 ppm, and continue – **Ctrl+space** will ‘unpause’ the simulation. Repeat, increasing **pCO₂atm** by 100ppm every 5d, until you have run the simulation at 1000 ppm. Watch the plots being developed over time.

Look at each of the graphs, and make sure you can explain what they show. Notice the changing composition of the dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), and compare with **Fig.5**. Can you explain the changing pattern of $\delta[\text{H}^+]$ as the system equilibrates to increases in pCO₂? Check the legend to **Fig.6**.

Repeat the whole process, but at lower or higher temperatures. How does temperature affect the pH, the composition of DIC and also $\delta[\text{H}^+]$? How might this potentially affect ocean acidification responses in polar (cold) vs tropical (warm) seas?

Effect of acidity on DIC composition

Here you can recreate the plot shown in **Fig.6**. To do this you are going to simulate the consequence of consuming (removing) CO₂ to increase the pH, and of producing (adding) CO₂ to decrease the pH. It is worth noting that the extremes to which you need to produce CO₂ within the system could not occur in nature as the nutrient levels could not be sufficiently high.

To start, set **Pause** = 5 d, **Wind** = 0 m/s, **Temperature** = 10°C, **pCO₂atm** = 400 ppm

Note that by setting **Wind** = 0, after the first 5d when the initial equilibrium condition is being set, the system is sealed, with no gas exchange between the air and water.

Run the model; when it automatically pauses at 5 d, set the slider for **Production** = 1 gC/m²/d, simulating a rate of photosynthesis, and continue – **Ctrl+space** will ‘unpause’ the simulation. Repeat, but do not allow the pH to increase much above 9.5, as the model will stop! (Above pH 9, the value of [H⁺] becomes so low that the model would need to run slower to capture the changes. A pH >9 is also lethal for most microalgae.)

Now, set the slider for **Production** = -1 gC/m²/d, simulating respiration (i.e., consumption which is the opposite of production), and continue; **Ctrl+space** will ‘unpause’ the simulation. Repeat, and watch as the pH decreases towards 6.

Once you have finished, try and explain the following graphs:

- carbonate chemistry
- pH vs [H⁺]
- [H⁺] and $\delta[\text{H}^+]$, and in particular how the value of $\delta[\text{H}^+]$ changes with pH (compare the graphs of pH vs time and $\delta[\text{H}^+]$ vs time). Remember – that the rates of change in CO₂ (the values of

Production) are of the same magnitude, +1 or -1. At which pH is the buffering capacity greatest, and how do you know?

Effects of biological activity

In many ways this is a repeat of the above study, but starting at different **pCO₂atm** and **Temperature**, and also using different values of **Wind**.

Here, **Wind** is not zero; the system is open for gas exchange between the air and water.

Design experiments to consider the effects of combinations of **pCO₂atm**, **Temperature**, **Wind** (which affects air-sea gas exchange rates), and **Production** values. Consider the following questions:

- With ocean acidification (i.e., at elevated **pCO₂atm**), how does the value of **Wind** interact with the rates of **Production**?
- For a microalgae that uses CO₂(aq), is the immediate consequence of ocean acidification likely to be 'good' or 'bad'?
- For consumers that eat the microalgae or degrade other organic material, hence producing CO₂, what is the immediate consequence of ocean acidification?
- How may your answer to the consumer question, above, be affected by whether the biomass being consumed is produced in the same water body (i.e., a consumption that immediately follows a production) versus the degradation of material that enters that water body from the land or with freshwater? To explore this, consider that for the former, you would first have a production of biomass which would consume CO₂ (pH↑) followed by a consumption of the same amount of biomass (and no more!) that would produce CO₂ (pH↓). For the latter, the water could receive a large amount of organic C from outside of the marine ecosystem, consumption of which would only lead the pH in one direction.
- How may growth in cold polar conditions differ with ocean acidification versus that in warm tropical conditions?

From the above you will appreciate how complex interactions with ocean acidification can become. In **EXPERIMENT 2** you will consider complications due to calcification (a common physiological feature of marine organisms), and in **EXPERIMENT 3** you will consider what happens during activities within a food web.

Caveats

As complex as all of the above may seem, the model itself gives a very simple description of the ecosystem (the physics, chemistry and biology). As with all models, it is good practice to consider the consequences of such simplifications.

What is missing?

What is present but is perhaps simplified too much?

In what ways is the model useful, and in what ways is it not?

EXPERIMENT 2: Calcification and alkalisation experiments

Calcification, the process of the formation of CaCO_3 into what is generically termed 'limestone', affects pH. Calcification in nature occurs not only in animals (for the formation of shells and bones), but also in certain microbes, and notably by microalgae called coccolithophorids (Figs. 1, 4).

The process of the formation of CaCO_3 , although decreasing the dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) content of the water and essentially thus removing CO_2 from the water, also alters the total alkalinity by removing carbonate ions (CO_3^{2-} and Ca^{2+}).

In these experiments, using the model **ProBleu OA Exp2 CP.sip**, you can explore:

- the consequences of calcification by an animal on pH
- the consequences of calcification by a microalgae on pH
- the concept of alkalisation as a means to combat ocean acidification

These explorations can be conducted in systems that have been configured for seawater equilibrated to an atmosphere of different pCO_2 , and also in water of different temperature.

NOTE: The model is a development of that used for **EXPERIMENT 1**; you should complete **EXPERIMENT 1** before proceeding.

For each of the following studies, you need to select the required pCO_2 atm

Note that **the system is sealed** (after the first 5d while equilibrium is set with your selected pCO_2 atm), with no gas exchange between the air and water.

Select the required temperature and atmospheric pCO_2 . Preindustrial pCO_2 was ca. 300 ppm, the current value is ca. 450 ppm; under extreme climate change projections it could attain 1000 ppm. During the first 5d of the simulation time the system will equilibrate, with **pH** and **[H⁺]** plotting a steady line and the value of **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** (that is, the rate of change of acidity) settling to a value of zero.

Changes in acidity; how to interpret the value of $\delta[\text{H}^+]$

Acidity is described by the proton concentration, as $[\text{H}^+]$. Recall that pH is just a (negative log) transform of $[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig.2). Because pH is a log transform, it is inappropriate to simply refer to changes in pH (such as increases or decreases in pH by 0.5) without providing its initial value. More usefully then, we should refer to changes in $[\text{H}^+]$. The mathematical symbol for changes over time is the Greek lowercase letter δ (delta). We thus refer to rates of change in acidity as **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** . A positive value indicates acidity is increasing ($\text{pH}\downarrow$); a negative value that acidity is decreasing ($\text{pH}\uparrow$).

You may note that under constant rates of addition or removal of CO_2 , the value of **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** increases or decreases over time while the **pH** is changing. What this is telling you is that, for a given change in addition or removal of CO_2 the acidity is changing by a different amount because the pH is moving out of (indicated by **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** increasing), or into (indicated by **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** decreasing) the zone of highest buffering capacity of the carbonate system.

Also, note that there are two plots of **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** against time, one of which ('**detailed scale**') gives detail for values for **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** between -1.5 to 1.5; use this detailed plot to help judge whether the system is at equilibrium with no change in pH, such that **$\delta[\text{H}^+] = 0$** . There is a thin black line at **$\delta[\text{H}^+] = 0$** to help you clearly see this equilibrium point, and the current value is given in the box next to the graph.

The model interface

Below is a screenshot of the model interface, showing the 'Explore' page

Fig.A2 Screenshot of an example from the *Explore* page of the model.

The image in **Fig.A2** is annotated to show the following:

- Buttons to control **temperature** and **CaCO₃ addition** (the latter is used to explore alkalisation).
- Sliders to control **pCO₂atm**, **production** (+ve for photosynthesis, consuming CO₂, -ve for consumption with respiration, producing CO₂), the **f-ratio** (1 uses only nitrate, 0 uses only ammonium for the support of production – see also **Table 1**), and organism **Ca:C** to control calcification.
- Table showing pCO₂atm and the current acidity, and graphs of pCO₂aq and pCO₂atm against time. The value of pCO₂atm mirrors the value you set.
- Graphs showing pH and acidity (i.e., [H⁺], nanomole H⁺ Kg⁻¹) changing over time.
- Graphs showing carbonate chemistry vs pH and how this changes over time in the simulation.
- Graphs showing production and f-ratio changing over time; these mirror the settings you have made.
- Graphs showing changing total alkalinity (TA) and Ca:C over time. The graph of Ca:C mirrors the settings you have made.

viii) Graphs showing changes in acidity, i.e., $\delta[\text{H}^+]$; the lefthand plot shows detail around $\delta[\text{H}^+] = 0$, with the black line showing zero change. The current value is reported in the box.

Explorations

Calcification by animals

Animals are consumers, so **Productivity** is negative; these organisms produce CO_2 .

The values of **CaCO₃ addition** (this must be set to 0 for now) and of the **f ratio** are not needed here.

First set **Productivity** = -0.1 and **CaC** = 0 and run the model at your selected **pCO₂atm** and **T**, observing the direction of the change in **pH** and **[H⁺]**, and also the value of **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** .

Now repeat, but setting **CaC** at a moderate value. This is now simulating a rate of growth of consumers that couples their respiration rate, which will correlate with their growth rate, with a rate of calcification (for shell formation, for example). What happens to **pH** and **[H⁺]**, and also the value of **$\delta[\text{H}^+]$** ?

Repeat again using a higher value of **CaC** (higher calcification, thicker shells, for example) and different **negative** values of **Productivity** (i.e., different growth rates of the consumer). Try again with different values of **pCO₂atm** and **Temp**.

Note here that temperature (**Temp**) in this experiment is only affecting the temperature of the seawater and hence the carbonate chemistry. In reality, changing temperature would also affect the rate of animal growth and thus the value of the negative production rate. Note also that the system used here is closed to the atmosphere (**Wind** = 0), while in reality the rates of change you observe in the model would be affected by gas exchange and thence re-equilibration of the carbonate chemistry (**Fig.5**). You will explore a system open to gas exchange in **Experiment 3**.

Explain:

- what is happening, and why.
- what is happening to the CO_2 (check **pCO₂**, though noting that DIC is decreasing). Is calcification (the removal of CO_2) increasing or decreasing the contribution of CO_2 to DIC, and hence is calcification likely to result in the release of CO_2 from the seawater into the atmosphere?
- why does the rate of change in acidity (**$\delta[\text{H}^+]$**) increase as pH decreases?
- why does total alkalinity (TA) decrease?

Calcification by microalgae

Some photosynthetic plankton also calcify. These include the coccolithophorids that are visible from space as giving pale white-green growths (**Figs.1, 4a,b**) and also some foraminifera, a type of plankton that acquires the ability to photosynthesize by stealing the chloroplasts from algal prey. For the foraminifera, CaCO_3 provides a skeleton supporting the cellular structure. Exactly why the coccolithophorids produce plates of CaCO_3 is unknown; suggestions have included as providing protection against grazers or viruses, as a reflectant against high light at the sea surface, or as helping photosynthesis by raising the concentration of $\text{CO}_2(\text{aq})$ next to the cell. Here, you will explore what may just be a consequence of calcification, or perhaps a contributing explanation for why these organisms make coccoliths. Whatever the reason for coccolith formation, this activity has, over geological time, been of importance for the deposition of what we see as limestone cliffs such as the White Cliffs of Dover.

From **EXPERIMENT 1**, you will know that photosynthesis, by removing CO₂, causes a basification; pH increases. This process decrease the availability of CO₂ needed for photosynthesis. From your first trials with **EXPERIMENT 2** you will know that the process of calcification decreases pH and increases the availability of CO₂. We may hypothesize that microalgae would be best equipped to balance photosynthesis (raising pH) and calcification (decreasing pH).

To start, the values of **CaCO₃ addition** must be set = 0.

First set **Productivity** = 0.1, **f-ratio** = 1; this means that growth is supported by the use of nitrate (NO₃⁻). Set **CaC** = 0 for no calcification and run the model at your selected **pCO_{2atm}** and **Temp**, observing the direction of the change in **pH** and **[H⁺]**, and also the value of **δ[H⁺]**. You can explore what happens when you change **f-ratio** during the run (at each pause event), but then repeat the run with a single set of values and record the pH at time 20d.

Repeat, but with **f-ratio** = 0; this means that growth is supported by the use of ammonium NH₄⁺. Record the pH at time 20d. What difference do you see? How does the f-ratio affect pH during growth?

Now repeat the above steps but with **CaC** = 1. You can explore what happens when you change **CaC** during the run (at each pause event), but then repeat the run with a single set of values and record the pH at time 20d. Note also the value of **PIC:POC**; this is the ratio of C in the microalgae between the chalk CaCO₃ plates on the outside of the cell (particulate inorganic C – PIC) to the particulate organic C (POC) of its biomass.

Repeat the above steps, using different values of **CaC**, to investigate the following:

- What value of **CaC**, and thence of PIC:POC, provides a balance between the effects of photosynthesis and calcification? – you can judge that balance by **δ[H⁺] = 0**. The PIC:POC ratio in samples taken from nature are often around a value of 1; how does this compare to the values in the simulation?
- How is that balance point affected by the **f-ratio**? Does using nitrate or ammonium require a higher or lower **CaC** to achieve **δ[H⁺] = 0**?
- How is that balance affected by **pCO_{2atm}** and/or **Temp**? (you may wish to set **f-ratio** = 0.5 for this exploration)

Alkalinisation

Alkalinisation has been suggested as a means to combat ocean acidification. In simple terms, you may consider this as the opposite of calcification. You have seen (above) how calcification, although decreasing DIC, increases acidity (i.e., decreases pH). The idea here is to dissolve CaCO₃ in seawater. Intuitively, you will thus know the answer to what happens. However, here you can explore how much CaCO₃ you need to reverse ocean acidification, starting at different equilibria points of atmospheric pCO₂ and at different temperatures.

To explore alkalinisation isolated from other events, first disable the biological activity; set **Productivity**=0. Note that clicking your pointing device just above or below the slider moves it to an exact value, as indicated on the scale.

The Ca:C value for CaCO₃ = 3.3368; so, set the slider for **CaC** to a value around 3.34.

Run the model with your selected **pCO_{2atm}** and **Temp**.

Set **CaCO₃ addition** to 0.5 (g Ca m⁻² d⁻¹). What happens to the pH? What happens to the total alkalinity (TA)?

Repeat with **CaCO₃ addition** at 1, change the value during the model run.

Repeat the whole process with different values of **pCO₂atm** and **T**. For a given value of **CaCO₃ addition**, how does **δ[H⁺]** vary? Try to explain why.

NOTE: This amount of CaCO₃ (1g Ca = 2.5g of limestone) does not seem like much, but this is for just a body of water of 1m² and 1m deep. Just over an area of sea of 1Km², you would need (2.5x1000x1000)g = 2.5 tonnes of limestone, and then multiply by the depth of the water column. And this is for one day, ignoring any continuing input of atmospheric CO₂ that would be countering the effects of the alkalisation.

Caveats

As complex as all of the above may seem, the model itself gives a very simple description of the ecosystem (the physics, chemistry and biology). As with all models, it is good practice to consider the consequences of such simplifications.

What is missing?

What is present but is perhaps simplified too much?

In what ways is the model useful, and in what ways is it not?

EXPERIMENT 3: Ecological interactions

In **EXPERIMENT 1** and **EXPERIMENT 2** various facets of ocean acidification were explored. What was missing were the ecological feedbacks that occur in natural systems. Here, these facets are brought together by running a simple nutrient-microalgae-zooplankton model coupled to the description of the carbonate system that controls pH.

It must be stressed at the outset that we still know very little about the details of how acidity interacts with organism growth. What we do know is that organisms exhibit optimum conditions and that, as those conditions move away from optimal, rates of growth deteriorate. For the model used here, the same relationship between pH and optimum conditions for growth is used for both organism groups represented in the model.

The appearance of the response curve between pH and organism health is shown in **Fig.A3**. The shape of the curve is informed by research on real plankton organisms (Flynn et al. 2015). You may wish to consider how the model would behave if the organisms exhibited different forms of the response curve.

Fig.A3 Response curves relating the growth potential of an organism to the seawater pH. The optimal pH shown here is around 8.3, at which the maximum growth rate may be attained. In the graph, this condition provides a value of pH-regulation (pHreg) =1. However, the breadth of the effect changes with the health of the organism; it is widest when the organism is most healthy (Health 1), and narrows as health deteriorates. This is an example of a multi-stressor interaction.

The ecological model is very simple (**Fig.A4**), comprising a single microalgae type that consumes the nutrient ammonium. The microalgae are eaten by a single zooplankton type. The nutrient is recycled, including from the decay of detritus originating as voided part-digested material. The microalgae can continue to grow for a while after the exhaustion of the nutrient, accumulating excess carbon as lipid. In so doing, they continue to convert CO₂ into biomass, while their changing biomass composition also becomes less advantageous to the zooplankton predator. So, a zooplankton consuming a poor quality microalgae grows less efficiently, releasing more C as debris but also releasing less ammonium. In consequence of these events, noting that there is a continuing exchange of CO₂ between the atmosphere and the water, the timing of the growth of the two organism groups has important implications for the changing concentration of CO₂ and hence the changes of the seawater pH.

Fig.A4 Diagram showing all the feedbacks as described by the ecological model. The transfer of nutrients to support the growth of microalgae depends on the amount of nutrient in the system at the start, and the amount of microalgae biomass (i). Growth of the microalgae, in terms of carbon, can continue for a while after exhaustion of the nutrient, as the microalgae accumulates excess C as lipid and sugar. The transfer of material from the microalgae to support the growth of zooplankton depends on the amount of microalgal biomass (the food), the quality of the microalgae (how much excess C it contains), and the amount of zooplankton biomass (ii). The total direct return of nutrient from zooplankton that is lost during their growth due to inefficiencies depends on the zooplankton biomass and quality of the microalgae (iii). There is an additional return of nutrient from decaying zooplankton faeces, which depends on how quickly they feed on the microalgae (iv); to this is added returns following death of the zooplankton if they starve of food.

Fig.A5 shows a summary of the processes described by the model.

Fig.A5 Interactions between the ecology shown in **Fig.A4** and acidity. Increased atmospheric CO_2 ($pCO_2(atm)$) increases aquatic CO_2 ($pCO_2(aq)$); (i), with the equilibrium affected by gas exchange rates influenced by wind speed etc. Increased $pCO_2(aq)$ increases acidity (ii); depending on the pH, the acidity may enhance or depress growth rates of the microalgae and zooplankton (iii; see **Fig.A3**). Microalgal growth, consuming CO_2 , decreases acidity (iv). Microalgal growth consumes nutrients (v), having a minor influence on total alkalinity (not shown). Zooplankton consume microalgae (vi), directly and indirectly (via decay of debris) regenerating nutrients (vii), and increasing acidity through production of CO_2 (viii). Some microalgae produce plates of calcium carbonate ('cocoliths'); this process decrease total alkalinity (ix), which increases acidity (x). During zooplankton feeding on calcified microalgae, cocoliths may be digested (xi), a process that increases TA (xii) and thus decreases acidity.

This model describes interactions between microalgae and zooplankton, with nutrient recycling and interactions with nutrient load and pH. In addition, the microalgae can be configured as a calcifying organism.

You can alter:

- atmospheric $p\text{CO}_2$ (affecting acidification)
- degree of air-sea gas exchange (realised by altering the wind speed)
- nutrient load (affecting biomass growth)
- initial biomass of the zooplankton relative to the microalgae (affecting bloom dynamics)
- calcification of the microalgae (production of coccoliths, altering alkalinity)
- the extent of dissolution of calcium carbonate plates (coccoliths) during predation

In these experiments, using the **ProBleu OA Exp3 CP.sip** model, you can explore responses to the following:

- the interactions between bloom dynamics and pH
- the effects of calcification (production of coccoliths) by the microalgae
- the consequential degree of dissolution of the coccoliths during prey digestion, on pH

The model interface

Below is a screenshot of the model interface, showing the 'Explore' page

Fig.A6 Screenshot of an example from the *Explore* page of the model.

The image in **Fig.A6** is annotated to show the following:

- i) Buttons to control **Wind** speed (0=isolated from atmosphere), the size of the zooplankton population at the start (**Z inoc**), and dissolution of coccoliths (if produced by the microalgae; **CaCO₃ dis**).
- ii) Sliders to control **pCO_{2atm}**, nutrient availability (**N-load**) and the level of calcification (synthesis of coccoliths) by the microalgae (**CaC**). To place the **N-load** in context, mid-ocean conditions have a low N-load (i.e., the sum of all forms of N as nutrients, organisms and detritus) of around 70 mgN m⁻³. Moving closer to the land, N-loading is higher; values >280 mgN m⁻³ are indicative of increasing eutrophication.
- iii) Shows the current pCO_{2atm} and acidity, and also the PIC:POC ratio as a consequence of the value of CaC in the microalgae.
- iv) Graphs showing allocations of C and N in the model.

For C, these are; dissolved inorganic carbon (**DIC**), microalgae (**C_{phy}**), zooplankton (**C_{zoo}**), as particulate calcium carbonate (**chalk_C**) either attached to microalgae or suspended in the water, the voided organic carbon as debris and faecal material (**VOC**), the sum of all the above as system-C (**sysC**; if the system is isolated, this value should be constant).

For N, these are: nutrient (**Am**), microalgae (**N_{phy}**; note that the ratio between N_{phy}:C_{phy} changes, decreasing if Am is exhausted), debris and faecal material (**VON**), the sum of all the above as system-N (**sysN**; if the system is isolated, this value should be constant).

- v) Graph showing the pH effects on the growth of microalgal (**pHreg**) and zooplankton (**pHreg_Z**). These values of pHreg indicate optimal conditions (value 1) or extremely poor conditions (value 0); **Fig.A3**.
- vi) Graph showing the flux of CO₂ into or out of the water. A +ve value indicates a flow of CO₂ from the air into the ocean.
- vii) Graphs showing changes over time in the carbonate chemistry composition, and **pCO_{2(aq)}** and **pCO_{2(atm)}**. The value of pCO_{2(atm)} mirrors that set at the start of the simulation.
- viii) Graphs showing changes over time in pH and total alkalinity
- ix) Graphs showing changes in acidity (as nanomole H⁺ Kg⁻¹) and δ[H⁺] (the black line shows zero change).

IMPORTANT NOTE: The following tests are collectively complex, so you need to work through systematically. After each simulation it will be helpful to copy the 'Explore' screen, including the setting (so you have a record of the test) as well as the output graphs, and save it in (for example) a PowerPoint slide for future comparison between different tests.

NOTE: You can also use different input values to those suggested. Try and be logical in your approach; planning a matrix of variables to change will be useful. It may be helpful to conduct some initial explorations using the suggestions given below, and then revisit aspects in greater detail.

Explorations

Effects of N-loading

Set the following buttons: **Wind** = 0, **Z inoc** = 5%, **CaCO₃ dis** = 0.

Set the following sliders: **pCO₂atm** = 300, **N-Load** = 280, **CaC** = 0 (this prevents calcification).

Run the model and try to relate the changes in the plots to each other. Note that the system-C (sysC in the 'Carbon' graph) is constant; there is no exchange with the atmosphere because **Wind** = 0.

Repeat with **N-load** = 560. How has this affected the dynamics of the phytoplankton-zooplankton growth? How has it affected the acidity, DIC, and pHreg? (Recall that the value of pHreg indicates how pH is affecting the physiology of the organisms; a value of 1 indicates optimal conditions, while a value of 0 indicates lethal pH conditions – **Fig.A3.**)

What is the effect of starting with a lower **Z inoc** setting? This alters not only the timing of the growth of the predator and of the microalgal bloom (the separation of these is termed 'mis-match'), but if the nutrient is exhausted then the quality of the microalgae as food deteriorates. This affects the rate of respiration that recycles nutrients and CO₂ back into the system, and will thus affect changes in seawater acidity.

NOTE: Mid-ocean conditions have a low N-load (i.e., the sum of all forms of N as nutrients, organisms and detritus) of around 70 mgN m⁻³; this equates to 5µM inorganic N-nutrient. Moving closer to the land, N-loading is higher. Values >280 mgN m⁻³ are indicative of increasing eutrophication.

Effects of pCO₂atm

Repeat the 'Effects of N-loading' test, still with **Wind** = 0, but with **pCO₂atm** = 600, with **N-load** = 280, and then = 560.

How are the results different compared to when **pCO₂atm** = 300? Can you explain why there are differences (check your understanding from earlier experiments).

Effects of gas exchange

Repeat the 'Effects of N-loading' and 'Effects of pCO₂atm' tests, but now with **Wind** = 10.

How do the results differ to those you obtained before. In particular, note that the system-C (sysC in the 'Carbon' graph) is no longer constant; there is an exchange of CO₂ between the atmosphere and the water (see the 'CO₂ flux' graph).

Effects of calcification

Restart and repeat the 'Effects of N-loading' tests (**Wind** = 0, **Z inoc** = 5%, **CaCO₃ dis** = 0) but now with **CaC** = 3. This now enables calcification by the microalgae.

Repeat to test what happens when **CaCO₃ dis** = 0, or = 0.5, or = 1. Recall that **CaCO₃ dis** is describing the proportion of **CaCO₃** (i.e., chalk) made by the microalgae that dissolves during grazing by the zooplankton.

Can you adjust **CaC** (and thence the PIC:POC ratio) so that the acidity during the microalgal bloom is unchanged? What happens when you use different values of **CaCO₃ dis**? How is total alkalinity (TA) affected?

Repeat the above, but with **pCO₂atm** = 600, and then repeat it all again with **Wind** = 10.

NOTE: The selection of certain combinations of high nutrient levels (N-load), microalgal calcification (CaC), low CaCO₃ dissolution (CaCO₃ dis), and low rates of gas exchange (affected by Wind),

can collectively push the system to extremes at which point pHreg will fall to low values. The model may even stop. When such results are seen, ask yourself whether the test conditions are plausible.

Caveats

As complex as all of the above may seem, the model itself gives a very simple description of the ecosystem (the physics, chemistry and biology). As with all models, it is good practice to consider the consequences of such simplifications.

What is missing?

What is present but is perhaps simplified too much?

In what ways is the model useful, and in what ways is it not?

Appendix 2 What you should have noted from the simulations

EXPERIMENT 1

Effects of altering atmospheric CO₂

Increasing pCO₂ increases acidity (pH ↓, [H⁺]↑).

As pH decreases, a given change in pCO₂ results in a larger $\delta[H^+]$. This is because the pH falls below the zone of maximum buffering capacity. This means that ocean acidification becomes increasingly problematic as the event develops.

Temperature alters the equilibrium point for the carbonate buffering system. Polar region will be most affected as their temperature is also showing the greatest rate of change.

Effect of acidity on DIC composition

pH radically affects the composition of DIC. Ocean acidification increases the concentration of CO₂, which may benefit certain microalgae that exploit this DIC source for photosynthesis; the others use bicarbonate but the concentration of that remains very high.

Changes in buffering capacity are apparent from the rate of change of acidity, as $\delta[H^+]$.

Effects of biological activity

Productivity affects pH. A +ve production (i.e., photosynthesis exceeds consumption) increases pH. With ocean acidification that increase in pH is initially faster than it used to be when pCO₂(atm) was lower; this is because the buffering capacity is lower under OA. The pH then increases through the zone of highest buffering capacity and then enters a zone of low buffering capacity at high pH.

In general, OA is not necessarily detrimental for microalgae; they have better access to CO₂ and the amount of production possible before pH rises to dangerous levels (ca. > pH 9) is greater. This may enable larger blooms to develop with eutrophication, enhancing the likelihood of hypoxia.

See the companion project - **Flynn KJ Lessin G (2025) Getting too warm: exploring effects of temperature upon aquatic ecosystems – a teaching guide. Zenodo**
<https://doi.org/10.5281/17522204>.

Consumption, -ve production, produces CO₂. This acidifies the water. Starting in water under OA, the change in pH is faster than it used to be, as the buffering capacity is lower.

In general, OA may be seen as detrimental for consumers.

Elevated gas exchange rates (high wind), counters the effects of biological activity on pH.

Caveats

This model is stripped right back to essentials, to enable an exploration of only the basics, with no biological feedbacks and uses prescribed fixed rates of production.

EXPERIMENT 2

Calcification by animals

Calcification by animals causes pH to decrease. Although the process removes CO₂, the changes to the carbonate system results in the release of H⁺. As OA develops, so the starting pH is lower, this acidification increases [H⁺] more because of the deteriorating buffering capacity of the carbonate system under OA. This situation is expected to be most problematic for animals in benthic nearshore systems which are dominated by consumption rather than production. This is because the consumption itself lowers pH below the bulk water level, further exacerbating the decline in the buffering capacity of the carbonate system.

Calcification by microalgae

By careful adjustment you will find that the optimal CaC value, at which acidification from calcification is balanced by basification from photosynthesis, varies with whether the microalgae are using nitrate or ammonium (defined by the f-ratio). The use of ammonium itself imparts an acidification; the use of nitrate does the opposite.

The balance point changes with ocean acidification, and the effect of the f-ratio becomes more marked as the pH is moved below the optimal buffering zone.

See Flynn et al. (2016) for more information on this topic.

Alkalinisation

Dissolving CaCO₃ (chalk) increases the total alkalinity (TA). This results in the pH increasing, compensating for OA. The further away from the historic value of pCO₂(atm) (ca. 300 ppm), the greater the addition is required.

Caveats

This model is stripped right back to essentials, to enable an exploration of only the basics, with no biological feedbacks and uses prescribing fixed rates of production.

EXPERIMENT 3

Effects of N-loading

Changes in pH with ecology are greater with higher biomass abundance, and therefore with high nutrient loads. If the mismatch between zooplankton and microalgae is greater, then the microalgal bloom develops further so pH increases more, and then when the zooplankton consumption does dominate, the pH decreases further (i.e., the [H⁺] oscillation is greater). Set against the multi-stressor interaction with organism health (**Fig.A3**), such changes could prove lethal.

Effects of pCO₂atm

With elevated pCO₂atm, the changes are greater, for a given nutrient load. This is because, under OA, the start conditions are outside of the zone of maximum buffering capacity of the carbonate system.

Effects of gas exchange

Gas exchange rates have an important effect on ecosystem-driven changes in acidity. The oscillations in [H⁺] are greatest in calm conditions.

Biological activity has important consequences for the drawing down of CO₂ from the atmosphere during production, and conversely the release of CO₂ back into the atmosphere when dominated by consumption. Note that the system-C is not constant when Wind >0 and that the gas exchange interacts with biological activity.

Effects of calcification

Calcification of the microalgae, and whether the chalky coccoliths are dissolved during predation by the zooplankton, has profound effects on seawater acidity. It is possible now to generate a situation where production no longer causes basification (because acidification during calcification balances with basification during photosynthesis), but of course consumption of the newly produced microalgal biomass still causes acidification. If the coccoliths dissolve within the same water body (normally they sink), so raising TA and pH, then the balance is reset.

Caveats

The model does not account for temperature control on biology. Besides affecting the chemistry of the carbonate buffering system, temperature radically affects biological processes. An increase in temperature by just a few degrees may change the whole ecosystem functioning, disturbing the balance of production and consumption.

The ecosystem description in the model is very simple. A real system has hundreds of components each with its own impacts on acidity and each affected by acidity. Very few studies have been made of such interactions in a way that can contribute to the construction of complex simulation models. See Cripps et al. (2014, 2016) and Flynn et al. (2015).

In reality, the production and consumption of biomass, and the dissolution of coccoliths, occur at different depths in the water column. Only production at the very surface is directly and rapidly affected by gas exchange and thus the flux of CO₂ in/out of the water column.

In consequence of the above issues, the models of ecology involving OA can only provide a general overview of events and point at potential consequences for ecosystem functioning.

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